

Supplementary Information

A modular synthetic strategy towards fast-growing poly(amide-carbosilane) dendrimers based on click chemistry and organic solvent nanofiltration

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1. Detailed synthesis and characterization of compounds

Dendritic core G₀-N. Cysteamine hydrochloride (2.11 g, 18.6 mmol, 4.00 eq.) and DMPA (0.18 g, 0.69 mmol, 0.15 eq.) were put into a 40 mL vial, MeOH (25 mL) and tetraallylsilane (892 mg, 4.64 mmol, 1.00 eq.) were added and the reaction mixture was purged with argon during stirring for 10 min. The reaction mixture was irradiated in the TEC reaction (see General procedure GP2) for 15 min while stirring. The solvent was removed on a rotary evaporator to afford G₀-N (3.00 g, quantitative yield, beige powder, further used without any purification with DMPA). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 8.22 (br s, 12H, NH₃), 2.93 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 8H, CH₂N), 2.74 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 8H, CH₂CH₂N), 2.56 (t, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 8H, CH₂(CH₂)₂Si), 1.54–1.47 (m, 8H, SiCH₂CH₂), 0.63–0.59 (m, 8H, SiCH₂). **¹³C {¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹³C HSQC, ¹H-¹³C HMBC): δ 38.6 (NCH₂), 34.4 (Si(CH₂)₂CH₂), 27.8 (NCH₂CH₂), 23.7 (SiCH₂CH₂), 11.1 (SiCH₂). **²⁹Si {¹H} NMR** (79 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 3.66. **HRMS** (ESI⁺): *m/z* (monoisotopic) calcd. for [C₂₀H₄₉N₄S₄Si]⁺ 501.2604, found 501.2590 [M-3HCl-Cl]⁺.

Methyl 4-(3-(triallylsilyl)propoxy)benzoate, MeO-AB₃ module. Methyl 4-hydroxybenzoate (5.00 g, 32.9 mmol) and calcinated K₂CO₃ (9.08 g, 65.7 mmol) were dissolved in MeCN (375 mL) and triallyl(3-iodopropyl)silane (9.46 g, 29.6 mmol) was added. The reaction mixture was stirred at reflux for 20 h. Then, the solution was filtered through a filter paper (washed with DCM) and the solvents were removed on a rotary evaporator. The obtained mixture was separated on a short column of silica gel (50 g) in eluent pentane/Et₂O 10:1 (the product came as the first fraction). The solvents were removed giving yellow-orange viscous liquid (9.74 g, 95 %). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 7.98 (m, 2H, CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}CONH), 6.89 (m, 2H, CH_{Ph}), 5.80 (ddt, *J* = 16.9, 10.1, 8.1 Hz, 3H, CHCH₂), 4.94–4.87 (m, 6H, CHCH₂), 3.95 (t, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 2H, OCH₂), 3.88 (s, 3H, Me), 1.86–1.81 (m, 2H, OCH₂CH₂), 1.63 (dt, *J* = 8.1, 1.2 Hz, 6H, SiCH₂CH), 0.74–0.69 (m, 2H, SiCH₂CH₂). **¹³C {¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃, ¹H-¹³C HSQC, ¹H-¹³C HMBC): δ 167.0 (COOMe), 162.9 (C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 134.2 (CHCH₂), 131.7 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}), 122.5 (C_{q(Ph)}), 114.2 (CH_{Ph}), 114.0 (CHCH₂), 70.7 (OCH₂), 52.0 (Me), 23.4 (OCH₂CH₂), 19.6 (SiCH₂CH), 7.5 (SiCH₂CH₂). **²⁹Si {¹H} NMR** (79 MHz, CDCl₃): δ -0.11. **HRMS** (ESI⁺): *m/z* (monoisotopic) calcd. for [C₂₀H₂₉O₃Si]⁺ 345.1880, found 345.1875 [M+H]⁺; calcd. for [C₂₀H₂₈NaO₃Si]⁺ 367.1700, found 367.1700 [M+Na]⁺; calcd. for [C₄₀H₅₆NaO₆Si₂]⁺ 711.3508, found 711.3488 [2M+Na]⁺.

4-(3-(Triallylsilyl)propoxy)benzoic acid, AB₃ module. Methyl 4-(3-(triallylsilyl)propoxy)benzoate (9.74 g, 28.3 mmol) and KOH (7.93 g, 141 mmol) were dissolved in MeOH (190 mL) and the reaction mixture was stirred at reflux for 24 h. The solvent was reduced by half, DCM was added (500 mL) and the solution was washed (2 × 200 mL 1M HCl, 2 × 400 mL 3% aq. sol. of NaCl) and dried by anhydrous MgSO₄. The solvents were removed giving AB₃ module as a white amorphous solid (9.32 g, 98 %). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 8.06 (m, 2H, CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}CONH), 6.93 (m, 2H, CH_{Ph}), 5.80 (ddt, *J* = 16.9, 10.1, 8.1 Hz, 3H, CHCH₂), 4.94–4.87 (m, 6H, CHCH₂), 3.98 (t, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 2H, OCH₂), 1.87–1.83 (m, 2H, OCH₂CH₂), 1.64 (dt, *J* = 8.1, 1.2 Hz, 6H, SiCH₂CH), 0.75–0.71 (m, 2H, SiCH₂CH₂). **¹³C {¹H} NMR**

(101 MHz, CDCl₃, ¹H-¹³C HSQC, ¹H-¹³C HMBC): δ 171.9 (COOH), 163.7 (C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 134.2 (CHCH₂), 132.5 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}), 121.6 (C_{q(Ph)}), 114.3 (CH_{Ph}), 114.1 (CHCH₂), 70.8 (OCH₂), 23.4 (OCH₂CH₂), 19.7 (SiCH₂CH), 7.6 (SiCH₂). ²⁹Si {¹H} NMR (79 MHz, CDCl₃): δ -0.11. HRMS (ESI⁺): *m/z* (monoisotopic) calcd. for [C₁₉H₂₅O₃Si]⁻ 329.1578, found 329.1568 [M-H]⁻; calcd. for [C₃₈H₅₁O₆Si₂]⁺ 659.3230, found 659.3177 [2M-H]⁺.

Benzotriazolyl 4-(3-(triallylsilyl)propoxy)benzoate, activated BtO-AB₃ module. 4-(3-(triallylsilyl)propoxy)benzoic acid (2.49 g, 7.54 mmol, 1.10 eq. and more per amide bond) was activated as BtO-AB₃ module in reaction with TBTU (2.42 g, 7.54 mmol, 1.10 eq. and more per amide bond) and DIPEA (2.66 g, 20.63 mmol, 3.00 eq. per amide bond) during the synthesis of allylic dendrimers according to *General procedure GP1*. During the OSN, several filtrates containing solely the activated BtO-AB₃ module were collected, solvent was spontaneously evaporated under ambient air giving off-white needles in various yields depending on the excess in the reaction, 0.10 eq. and more per amide bond. The needles without further purification could be reused for the next synthesis of allylic dendrimer without further addition of TBTU (see *Recycling of modules AB₃ and AB₆* below). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 8.22 (m, 2H, CH_{Ph}), 8.09 (dd, *J* = 8.4, 1.1 Hz, 1H, CH_{BtO}), 7.54 (dd, *J* = 8.4, 6.7 Hz, 1H, CH_{BtO}), 7.47 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, 1H, CH_{BtO}), 7.43 (ddd, *J* = 8.1, 6.7, 1.1 Hz, 1H, CH_{BtO}), 7.04 (m, 2H, CH_{Ph}), 5.81 (ddt, *J* = 16.4, 10.1, 8.0 Hz, 3H, CHCH₂), 4.95–4.87 (m, 6H, CHCH₂), 4.03 (t, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 2H, OCH₂), 1.92–1.85 (m, 2H, OCH₂CH₂), 1.65 (dt, *J* = 8.1, 1.2 Hz, 6H, SiCH₂CH), 0.77–0.73 (m, 2H, O(CH₂)₂CH₂Si). ¹³C {¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃, ¹H-¹³C HSQC, ¹H-¹³C HMBC): δ 165.0 (C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 162.5 (COO), 143.7 (C_{qNBtO}), 134.2 (C_{q(Ph)}), 134.1 (CHCH₂), 133.2 (CH_{Ph}), 129.0 (C_{qNBtO}), 128.8 (CH_{BtO}), 124.9 (CH_{BtO}), 120.6 (CH_{BtO}), 115.1 (CH_{Ph}), 114.1 (CHCH₂), 108.6 (CH_{BtO}), 71.0 (OCH₂), 23.3 (OCH₂CH₂), 19.6 (SiCH₂CH), 7.6 (SiCH₂CH₂). HRMS (ESI⁺): *m/z* (monoisotopic) calcd. for [C₂₅H₂₉N₃NaO₃Si]⁺ 470.1870, found 470.1830 [M+Na]⁺.

1st generation dendrimers

G₁-3-A. Dendrimer G₁-3-A was prepared from 1.11 g (1.71 mmol) of G₀-N according to the general procedure for amidic coupling (see *General procedure GP1*). The product was purified by OSN using a 1kDa membrane in DCM/MeOH mixture, starting at 2:1 ratio and gradually increasing the polarity up to 1:2 so as to maintain the homogeneity of the solution, and obtained as a brownish viscous substance (2.67 g, 89 %). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 7.75 (m, 8H, CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}CONH), 6.88 (m, 8H, CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 6.78 (t, *J* = 5.7 Hz, 4H, NH), 5.79 (ddt, *J* = 16.5, 10.1, 8.1 Hz, 12H, CHCH₂), 4.91–4.86 (m, 24H, CHCH₂), 3.92 (t, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 8H, OCH₂), 3.59 (td, *J* = 6.6, 5.7 Hz, 8H, HNCH₂), 2.73 (t, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 8H, HNCH₂CH₂), 2.52 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 8H, Si(CH₂)₂CH₂S), 1.86–1.78 (m, 8H, OCH₂CH₂), 1.62 (dt, *J* = 8.1, 1.2 Hz, 24H, SiCH₂CH), 1.59–1.51 (m, 8H, SiCH₂CH₂), 0.72–0.68 (m, 8H, O(CH₂)₂CH₂), 0.63–0.59 (m, 8H, SiCH₂). ¹³C {¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃, ¹H-¹³C HSQC, ¹H-¹³C HMBC): δ 167.1 (HNCO), 161.8 (C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 134.2 (CHCH₂), 128.9 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}), 126.5 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}), 114.3 (CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 114.0 (CHCH₂), 70.7 (OCH₂), 39.2 (HNCH₂), 35.6 (Si(CH₂)₂CH₂S), 31.9 (CH₂CH₂NH), 24.4 (SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 23.4 (OCH₂CH₂), 19.6 (SiCH₂CH), 11.8 (SiCH₂(CH₂)₂S), 7.6 (CH₂(CH₂)₂O). ²⁹Si {¹H} NMR (79 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 3.65 (Si⁰), -0.10 (Si¹). HRMS (ESI⁺, CH₃OH): *m/z* (monoisotopic) calcd. for [C₉₆H₁₄₅N₄O₈S₄Si₅]⁺ 1749.8786; found 1749.8774 [M+H]⁺; calcd. for [C₁₉₂H₂₈₉KN₈O₁₆S₈Si₁₀]²⁺ 1768.8566, found [2M+H+K]²⁺; calcd. for [C₉₆H₁₄₄N₄NaO₈S₄Si₅]⁺ 1771.8606, found 1771.8557 (overlap) [M+Na]⁺; calcd. for [C₉₆H₁₄₆N₄O₈S₄Si₅]²⁺

875.4429, found 875.4429 $[M+2H]^{2+}$; calcd. for $[C_{96}H_{145}KN_4O_8S_4Si_5]^{2+}$ 894.4209, found 894.4164 $[2M+H+K]^{2+}$. **MALDI-TOF MS** (DCTB, Na^+): m/z (monoisotopic) calcd. for $[C_{96}H_{144}N_4NaO_8S_4Si_5]^+$ 1771.86, found 1771.89 $[M+Na]^+$.

G₁-3-N. Dendrimer G₁-3-N was prepared from 1.34 g (0.765 mmol) of dendrimer G₁-3-A according to General procedure GP2. The product was purified by OSN using 3kDa membrane in MeOH followed by lyophilization and obtained as a white powder (2.16 g, 91 %). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 8.57 (t, $J = 5.7$ Hz, 4H, NH), 8.23 (br s, 36H, NH_3^+), 7.83 (m, 8H, $CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}CONH$), 6.95 (m, 8H, $CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH_2$), 3.97 (t, $J = 5.8$ Hz, 8H, OCH_2), 3.38 (td, $J = 7.3, 5.7$ Hz, 8H, $HNCH_2$), 2.94 (t, $J = 7.4$ Hz, 24H, $CH_2NH_3^+$), 2.75 (t, $J = 7.4$ Hz, 24H, $CH_2CH_2NH_3^+$), 2.63 (t, $J = 7.3$ Hz, 8H, SCH_2CH_2NH), 2.55 (t, $J = 7.0$ Hz, 32H, $Si(CH_2)_2CH_2S$), 1.72–1.68 (m, 8H, OCH_2CH_2), 1.57–1.49 (m, 32H, $SiCH_2CH_2$), 0.66–0.60 (m, 40H, $SiCH_2$). **¹³C {¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹³C HSQC, ¹H-¹³C HMBC): δ 165.6 (HNCO), 160.9 ($C_{q(Ph)}OCH_2$), 129.0 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}), 126.4 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}), 113.9 ($CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH_2$), 70.2 (OCH_2), from HSQC 39.4 ($NHCH_2$), 38.6 ($CH_2NH_3^+$), 34.8 ($Si^0(CH_2)_2CH_2S$), 34.4 ($Si^1(CH_2)_2CH_2S$), 30.5 (SCH_2CH_2NH), 27.8 ($SCH_2CH_2NH_3^+$), 23.8 ($Si^0CH_2CH_2$), 23.7 ($Si^1CH_2CH_2$), 23.2 (OCH_2CH_2), 11.2 (Si^0CH_2), 11.1 ($Si^1CH_2(CH_2)_2S$), 7.7 ($O(CH_2)_2CH_2Si^1$). **²⁹Si {¹H} NMR** (79 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 4.05 (Si^1), 3.58 (Si^0). **HRMS** (ESI⁺, CH₃OH) m/z (monoisotopic): calcd. for $[C_{120}H_{229}N_{16}O_8S_{16}Si_5]^+$ 2674.2376, found 2674.2255 $[M-12HCl+H]^+$; calcd. for $[C_{120}H_{230}N_{16}O_8S_{16}Si_5]^{2+}$ 1337.6225, found 1337.6234 $[M-12HCl+2H]^{2+}$; calcd. for $[C_{120}H_{231}N_{16}O_8S_{16}Si_5]^{3+}$ 892.0841, found 892.0843 $[M-12HCl+3H]^{3+}$; calcd. for $[C_{120}H_{232}N_{16}O_8S_{16}Si_5]^{4+}$ 669.3149, found 669.3150 $[M-12HCl+4H]^{4+}$; calcd. for $[C_{120}H_{233}N_{16}O_8S_{16}Si_5]^{5+}$ 535.6534, found 535.6536 $[M-12HCl+5H]^{5+}$; calcd. for $[C_{120}H_{234}N_{16}O_8S_{16}Si_5]^{6+}$ 446.5457, found 446.5456 $[M-12HCl+6H]^{6+}$. **MALDI-TOF MS** (DHB, Na^+) m/z (monoisotopic): calcd. for $[C_{120}H_{229}N_{16}O_8S_{16}Si_5]^+$ 2674.24, found 2674.20 $[M+H]^+$; calcd. for $[C_{120}H_{228}N_{16}NaO_8S_{16}Si_5]^+$ 2696.22, found 2696.19 $[M+Na]^+$.

G₁-6-A. Dendrimer G₁-6-A was prepared from 748 mg (1.16 mmol) of G₀-N according to General procedure GP1. The product was purified by OSN using 3kDa membrane in DCM/MeOH mixture, starting at 2:1 ratio and gradually increasing the polarity up to 1:2 so as to maintain the homogeneity of the solution, and obtained as a brownish viscous substance (2.86 g, 95 %). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 6.89 (d, $J = 2.3$ Hz, 8H, CH_{Ph}), 6.70 (t, $J = 5.7$ Hz, 4H, NH), 6.54 (t, $J = 2.3$ Hz, 4H, CH_{Ph}), 5.79 (ddt, $J = 16.4, 10.0, 8.1$ Hz, 24H, $CHCH_2$), 4.93–4.86 (m, 48H, $CHCH_2$), 3.89 (t, $J = 6.6$ Hz, 16H, OCH_2), 3.59 (td, $J = 6.6, 5.7$ Hz, 8H, $HNCH_2$), 2.73 (t, $J = 6.6$ Hz, 8H, $HNCH_2CH_2$), 2.54 (t, $J = 7.2$ Hz, 8H, $SiCH_2CH_2CH_2S$), 1.81–1.77 (m, 16H, OCH_2CH_2), 1.62 (dt, $J = 8.1, 1.3$ Hz, 48H, $SiCH_2CH$), 1.63–1.61 (m, 8H, $SiCH_2CH_2$), 0.71–0.66 (m, 24H, $SiCH_2$). **¹³C {¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃, ¹H-¹³C HSQC, ¹H-¹³C HMBC): δ 167.4 (HNCO), 160.4 ($C_{q(Ph)}OCH_2$), 136.6 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}), 134.2 ($CHCH_2$), 114.0 ($CHCH_2$), 105.6 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}), 104.5 (CH_{Ph}), 70.9 (OCH_2), 39.3 ($HNCH_2$), 35.6 ($Si(CH_2)_2CH_2S$), 31.8 (CH_2CH_2NH), 24.4 ($SiCH_2CH_2CH_2S$), 23.5 (OCH_2CH_2), 19.6 ($SiCH_2CH$), 11.9 ($SiCH_2(CH_2)_2S$), 7.7 ($CH_2(CH_2)_2O$). **²⁹Si {¹H} NMR** (79 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 3.68 (Si^0), -0.11 (Si^1). **MALDI-TOF MS** (DHB, Na^+): m/z (monoisotopic) calcd. for $[C_{144}H_{224}N_4NaO_{12}S_4Si_9]^+$ 2604.37, found 2604.32 $[M+Na]^+$.

G₁-6-N. Dendrimer G₁-6-N was prepared from 1.44 g (0.557 mmol) of dendrimer G₁-6-A according to General procedure GP2. The product was purified by OSN using 3kDa membrane in MeOH followed by lyophilization and obtained as off-white powder (2.92 g, 98 %). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 8.79 (br s, 4H, NH), 8.30 (br s, 72H, NH₃⁺), 7.03 (br s, 8H, CH_{Ph}), 6.58 (br s, 4H, CH_{Ph}), 3.94 (t, *J* = 6.1 Hz, 16H, OCH₂), 3.37 (br s, 8H, CH₂NH), 2.94 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 48H, CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.76 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 48H, SCH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.63 (t, *J* = 6.9 Hz, 8H, SCH₂CH₂NH), 2.55 (t, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 56H, Si(CH₂)₂CH₂S), 1.72–1.64 (m, 16H, OCH₂CH₂), 1.55–1.51 (m, 56H, SiCH₂CH₂), 0.66–0.62 (m, 64H, SiCH₂). **¹³C {¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹³C HSQC, ¹H-¹³C HMBC): δ 165.6 (NHCO), 159.6 (C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 136.2 (HNCO_{C_{q(Ph)}}), 105.6 (HNCO_{C_{q(Ph)}}CH_{Ph}), 103.8 (CH_{Ph}), 70.4 (OCH₂), from HSQC 39.4 (CH₂NH), 38.7 (CH₂NH₃⁺), 34.8 (Si⁰(CH₂)₂CH₂S), 34.5 (Si¹(CH₂)₂CH₂S), 30.4 (SCH₂CH₂NH), 27.8 (SCH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 23.8 (Si⁰CH₂CH₂), 23.7 (Si¹CH₂CH₂), 23.3 (OCH₂CH₂), 11.3 (Si⁰CH₂), 11.2 (Si¹CH₂(CH₂)₂S), 7.8 (O(CH₂)₂CH₂Si¹). **²⁹Si {¹H} NMR** (79 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 4.02 (Si¹), 3.60 (Si⁰). **HRMS** (ESI⁺): *m/z* (100 % centroid) calcd. for [C₁₉₂H₃₉₄N₂₈O₁₂S₂₈Si₉]²⁺ 2218.5595, found 2218.5551 (96 %) [M-24HCl+2H]²⁺; calcd. for [C₁₉₂H₃₉₅N₂₈O₁₂S₂₈Si₉]³⁺ 1479.3754, found 1479.3750 [M-24HCl+3H]³⁺; calcd. for [C₁₉₂H₃₉₆N₂₈O₁₂S₂₈Si₉]⁴⁺ 1109.7834, found 1109.7828 [M-24HCl+4H]⁴⁺; calcd. for [C₁₉₂H₃₉₇N₂₈O₁₂S₂₈Si₉]⁵⁺ 888.0282, found 888.0278 [M-24HCl+5H]⁵⁺; calcd. for [C₁₉₂H₃₉₈N₂₈O₁₂S₂₈Si₉]⁶⁺ 740.1914, found 740.1912 [M-24HCl+6H]⁶⁺; calcd. for [C₁₉₂H₃₉₉N₂₈O₁₂S₂₈Si₉]⁷⁺ 634.5936, found 634.5937 [M-24HCl+7H]⁷⁺; calcd. for [C₁₉₂H₄₀₀N₂₈O₁₂S₂₈Si₉]⁸⁺ 555.3953, found 555.3954 [M-24HCl+8H]⁸⁺. **MALDI-TOF MS** (DHB, Na⁺): *m/z* (100 % centroid) calcd. for [C₁₉₂H₃₉₃N₂₈O₁₂S₂₈Si₉]⁺ 4436.11, found 4436.22 [M+H]⁺; calcd. for [C₁₉₂H₃₉₂N₂₈NaO₁₂S₂₈Si₉]⁺ 4458.09, found 4458.17 [M+Na]⁺.

2nd generation dendrimers

G₂-3-3-A. Dendrimer G₂-3-3-A was prepared from 1.17 g (0.376 mmol) of G₁-3-N according to General procedure GP1. The product was purified by OSN using 3kDa membrane in DCM/MeOH mixture, starting at 1:1 ratio and gradually increasing the polarity up to 1:2 so as to maintain the homogeneity of the solution, and obtained as a brownish viscous substance (2.26 g, 93 %). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 7.75 (m, 32H, CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}CONH), 7.03 (t, *J* = 5.7 Hz, 4H, NH), 6.87 (m, 32H, CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 6.85 (t, *J* = 5.7 Hz, 12H, NH), 5.78 (ddt, *J* = 16.5, 10.1, 8.1 Hz, 36H, CHCH₂), 4.92–4.85 (m, 72H, CHCH₂), 3.91 (t, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 32H, OCH₂), 3.57 (td, *J* = 6.6, 5.7 Hz, 32H, CH₂NH), 2.71 (t, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 32H, SCH₂CH₂NH), 2.52 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 32H, SCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), 1.85–1.77 (m, 24H, OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si²), 1.76–1.70 (m, 8H, OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si¹), 1.62 (dt, *J* = 8.1, 1.2 Hz, 72H, SiCH₂CH), 1.58–1.49 (m, 32H, SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 0.72–0.67 (m, 24H, O(CH₂)₂CH₂Si²), 0.66–0.60 (m, 8H, O(CH₂)₂CH₂Si¹, 24H, Si¹CH₂(CH₂)₂S), 0.58–0.56 (m, 8H, Si⁰CH₂), 13.3 (O¹CH₂), 70.6 (O⁰CH₂), 39.3 (CH₂N⁰H), 39.2 (CH₂N¹H), 35.6 (Si(CH₂)₂CH₂S), 31.9 (SCH₂CH₂NH), 24.4 (SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 23.7 (O⁰CH₂CH₂), 23.4 (O¹CH₂CH₂), 19.6 (SiCH₂CH), 11.8 (SiCH₂(CH₂)₂S), 8.2 (O⁰(CH₂)₂CH₂), 7.6 (O¹(CH₂)₂CH₂). **²⁹Si {¹H} NMR** (79 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 4.05 (Si¹), 3.61 (Si⁰), -0.11 (Si²).

MALDI-TOF MS (DCTB, Na⁺): *m/z* (100 % centroid) calcd. for [C₃₄₈H₅₁₆N₁₆NaO₃₂Si₁₇]⁺ 6449.08, found 6448.94 [M+Na]⁺.

G₂-3-3-N. Dendrimer G₂-3-3-N was prepared from 1.50 g (0.233 mmol) of dendrimer G₂-3-3-A according to General procedure GP2. The product was purified by OSN using 3kDa membrane in MeOH followed by lyophilization and obtained as a white powder (2.41 g, 98 %). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 8.59 (t, *J* = 6.0 Hz, 16H, NH), 8.25 (br s, 108H, NH₃⁺), 7.84 (m, 32H, CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}CONH), 6.94 (m, 32H, CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 3.95 (t, *J* = 6.3 Hz, 32H, OCH₂), 3.41–3.35 overlapped with H₂O (32H, CH₂NH), 2.94 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 72H, CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.75 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 72H, CH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.64 (t, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 32H, SCH₂CH₂NH), 2.55 (t, *J* = 7.0 Hz, 104H, SCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), 1.71–1.66 (m, 32H, OCH₂CH₂), 1.56–1.48 (m, 104H, SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 0.66–0.59 (m, 136H, SiCH₂). **¹³C {¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹³C HSQC, ¹H-¹³C HMBC): δ 165.6 (HNCO), 160.9 (C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 129.1 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}), 126.4 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}), 113.9 (CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 70.2 (OCH₂), from HSQC 39.5 (CH₂NH), 38.6 (CH₂NH₃⁺), 34.8 (CH₂S(CH₂)₂NH), 34.5 (CH₂S(CH₂)₂NH₃⁺), 30.5 (SCH₂CH₂NH), 27.8 (SCH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 23.8 (CH₂CH₂S(CH₂)₂NH), 23.7 (CH₂CH₂S(CH₂)₂NH₃⁺), 23.2 (OCH₂CH₂), 11.2 (CH₂(CH)₂S(CH₂)₂NH), 11.1 (CH₂(CH₂)₂S(CH₂)₂NH₃⁺), 7.7 (O(CH₂)₂CH₂). **²⁹Si {¹H} NMR** (79 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 4.04 (Si²), 3.99 (Si¹), 3.57 (Si⁰). **HRMS** (ESI⁺, CH₃OH): *m/z* (100 % centroid) calcd. for [C₄₂₀H₇₇₂N₅₂O₃₂S₅₂Si₁₇]⁴⁺ 2301.7989, found 2301.7956 (81 %) [M-36HCl+4H]⁴⁺; calcd. for [C₄₂₀H₇₇₃N₅₂O₃₂S₅₂Si₁₇]⁵⁺ 1841.6406, found 1841.6404 (97 %) [M-36HCl+5H]⁵⁺; calcd. for [C₄₂₀H₇₇₄N₅₂O₃₂S₅₂Si₁₇]⁶⁺ 1534.8684, found 1534.8672 (96 %) [M-36HCl+6H]⁶⁺; calcd. for [C₄₂₀H₇₇₅N₅₂O₃₂S₅₂Si₁₇]⁷⁺ 1315.7454, found 1315.7449 (99 %) [M-36HCl+7H]⁷⁺; calcd. for [C₄₂₀H₇₇₆N₅₂O₃₂S₅₂Si₁₇]⁸⁺ 1151.4031, found 1151.4025 (94 %) [M-36HCl+8H]⁸⁺; calcd. for [C₄₂₀H₇₇₇N₅₂O₃₂S₅₂Si₁₇]⁹⁺ 1023.5813, found 1023.5810 (99 %) [M-36HCl+9H]⁹⁺; calcd. for [C₄₂₀H₇₇₈N₅₂O₃₂S₅₂Si₁₇]¹⁰⁺ 921.3239, found 921.3234 (92 %) [M-36HCl+10H]¹⁰⁺; calcd. for [C₄₂₀H₇₇₉N₅₂O₃₂S₅₂Si₁₇]¹¹⁺ 837.6588, found 837.6588 (100 %) [M-36HCl+11H]¹¹⁺; calcd. for [C₄₂₀H₇₈₀N₅₂O₃₂S₅₂Si₁₇]¹²⁺ 767.9378, found 767.9370 (100 %, overlap) [M-36HCl+12H]¹²⁺; calcd. for [C₄₂₀H₇₈₁N₅₂O₃₂S₅₂Si₁₇]¹³⁺ 708.9432, found 708.9418 (96 %) [M-36HCl+13H]¹³⁺. **MALDI-TOF MS** (DHB, Na⁺): *m/z* (avg. mass) calcd. for [C₄₂₀H₇₆₉N₅₂O₃₂S₅₂Si₁₇]⁺ 9204.5, found 9204.9 [M+H]⁺.

G₂-3-6-A. Dendrimer G₂-3-6-A was prepared from 250 mg (80.9 μmol) of G₁-3-N according to General procedure GP1. The product was purified by OSN using 3kDa membrane in DCM/MeOH mixture 1:1 and obtained as a brownish viscous substance (665 mg, 92 %). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 7.75 (m, 8H, HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}), 6.89 (d, *J* = 2.3 Hz, 24H, HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}), 6.88 (m, 8H, CH_{Ph}), overlapped 6.87 (4H, NH), 6.77 (t, *J* = 5.7 Hz, 12H, NH), 6.53 (t, *J* = 2.3 Hz, 12H, CH_{Ph}), 5.78 (ddt, *J* = 16.5, 10.1, 8.1 Hz, 72H, CHCH₂), 4.92–4.86 (m, 144H, CHCH₂), 3.96–3.88 (t, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 56H, OCH₂), 3.58 (td, *J* = 6.6, 5.7 Hz, 32H, CH₂NH), 2.72 (t, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 32H, SCH₂CH₂NH), 2.54 (t, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 32H, SCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), 1.82–1.74 (m, 48H, OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si²), 1.64–1.54 (m, 8H, (OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si¹), 1.61 (dt, *J* = 8.1, 1.1 Hz, 144H, SiCH₂CH), 0.70–0.64 (m, 88H, SiCH₂). **¹³C {¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃, ¹H-¹³C HSQC, ¹H-¹³C HMBC): δ 167.4 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 167.2 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), 161.7 ((CH_{Ph})₂C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 160.4 (C_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂),

136.6 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 134.2 (CHCH₂), 129.0 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 126.7 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), 114.4 (CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 114.0 (CHCH₂), 105.6 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 104.5 (CH₂OC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 70.8 (OCH₂(CH₂)₂Si¹), 70.6 (OCH₂(CH₂)₂Si¹), 39.3 (CH₂NH), 35.6 (Si(CH₂)₂CH₂S), 31.9 (S¹CH₂CH₂NH), 31.8 (S²CH₂CH₂NH), 24.4 (SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 23.7 (OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si¹), 23.5 (OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si²), 19.6 (SiCH₂CH), 11.9 (SiCH₂(CH₂)₂S), 8.3 (O(CH₂)₂CH₂Si¹), 7.6 (O(CH₂)₂CH₂Si²). ²⁹Si {¹H} NMR (79 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 4.07 (Si¹), 3.62 (Si⁰), -0.11 (Si²). **MALDI-TOF MS** (DCTB, Na⁺): *m/z* (avg. mass) calcd. for [C₄₉₂H₇₅₆N₁₆NaO₄₄S₁₆Si₂₉]⁺ 8949.7 (avg. mass), found 8949.4 [M+Na]⁺.

G₂-3-6-N. Dendrimer G₂-3-6-N was prepared from 460 mg (51.5 μmol) of dendrimer G₂-3-6-A according to General procedure GP2. The product was purified by OSN using 3kDa membrane in MeOH followed by lyophilization and obtained as off-white powder (867 mg, 98 %). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 8.80 (br s, 12H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 8.66 (br s, 4H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), 8.31 (br s, 216H, NH₃⁺), 7.85 (m, 8H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}), 7.04 (s, 24H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}), 6.94 (m, 8H, CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 6.58 (s, 12H, CH_{Ph}), 3.94 (t, *J* = 7.0 Hz, 56H, OCH₂), overlapped with water (32H, CH₂NH), 2.94 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 144H, CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.76 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 144H, CH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.65 (t, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 32H, CH₂CH₂NH), 2.55 (t, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 176H, SCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), 1.70–1.66 (m, 56H, OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si), 1.56–1.49 (m, 176H, SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 0.66–0.61 (m, 232H, SiCH₂). ¹³C {¹H} NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹³C HSQC, ¹H-¹³C HMBC): δ 165.9 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), not detected or overlapped (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), 161.0 ((CH_{Ph})₂C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 159.6 (C_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 136.2 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 129.1 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 126.3 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), 113.8 (CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 105.7 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 103.9 (OC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}O), 70.4 (OCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), from HSQC 39.5 (CH₂NH), 38.7 (CH₂NH₃⁺), 34.8 (CH₂S(CH₂)₂NH), 34.5 (CH₂S(CH₂)₂NH₃⁺), 30.4 (CH₂CH₂NH), 27.8 (CH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 23.7 (CH₂CH₂S(CH₂)₂NH), 23.3 (CH₂CH₂O), 11.1 (SiCH₂(CH₂)₂S), 7.8 (SiCH₂(CH₂)₂O). ²⁹Si {¹H} NMR (79 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 4.02 (Si²), not detected or overlapped (Si^{0/1}). **MALDI-TOF MS** (DHB, Na⁺): *m/z* (avg. mass) calcd. for [C₆₃₆H₁₂₆₁N₈₈O₄₄S₈₈Si₂₉]⁺ 14482.2, found 14484.3 [M+H]⁺.

G₂-6-3-A. Dendrimer G₂-6-3-A was prepared from 318 mg (59.9 μmol) of G₁-6-N according to General procedure GP1. The product was purified by OSN using 3kDa membrane in DCM/MeOH mixture, starting at 2:3 ratio and gradually increasing the polarity up to 1:2 so as to maintain the homogeneity of the solution, and obtained as a brownish viscous substance (601 mg, 84 %). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 7.76 (m, 48H, HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}), 7.05 (t, *J* = 5.9 Hz, 24H, NH), 6.89 (d, *J* = 2.2 Hz, 8H, HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}), 6.89 (t, *J* = 5.9 Hz, 4H, NH), 6.85 (m, 48H, CH_{Ph}), 6.53 (t, *J* = 2.2 Hz, 4H, CH_{Ph}), 5.78 (ddt, *J* = 16.4, 10.1, 8.1 Hz, 72H, CHCH₂), 4.92–4.84 (m, 144H, CHCH₂), 3.90 (t, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 48H, OCH₂), 3.84 (t, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 16H, OCH₂), 3.56 (td, *J* = 6.8, 5.9 Hz, 56H, CH₂NH), 2.71 (t, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 56H, SCH₂CH₂NH), 2.51 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 56H, SCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), 1.84–1.76 (m, 48H, OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si²), 1.70–1.67 (m, 16H, OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si¹), 1.61 (dt, *J* = 8.1, 1.1 Hz, 144H, Si²CH₂CH), 1.56–1.54 (m, 56H, SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 0.71–0.59 (m, 120H, SiCH₂). ¹³C {¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃, ¹H-¹³C HSQC, ¹H-¹³C HMBC): δ 167.4 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 167.2 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), 161.8 ((CH_{Ph})₂C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 160.3 (C_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 136.6 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}),

134.2 (CHCH₂), 129.0 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 126.5 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), 114.3 (CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 114.0 (CHCH₂), 105.9 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 104.7 (CH₂OC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 70.8 (OCH₂(CH₂)₂Si¹), 70.7 (OCH₂(CH₂)₂Si²), 39.9 (CH₂NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 39.4 (CH₂NHCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), 35.6 (Si(CH₂)₂CH₂S), 31.8 (SCH₂CH₂NH), 24.4 (SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 23.8 (OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si¹), 23.4 (OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si²), 19.6 (SiCH₂CH), 11.8 (SiCH₂(CH₂)₂S), 8.3 (O(CH₂)₂CH₂Si¹), 7.6 (O(CH₂)₂CH₂Si²). **²⁹Si {¹H} NMR** (79 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 4.02 (Si¹), 3.62 (Si⁰), -0.11 (Si²). **MALDI-TOF MS** (DCTB, Na⁺): *m/z* (avg. mass) calcd. for [C₆₄₈H₉₆₈N₂₈NaO₆₀S₂₈Si₃₃]⁺ 11958.1, found 11958.2 [M+Na]⁺.

G₂-6-3-N. Dendrimer G₂-6-3-N was prepared from 200 mg (16.8 μmol) of dendrimer G₂-6-3-A according to General procedure GP2. The product was purified by OSN using 3kDa membrane in MeOH followed by lyophilization and obtained as a white powder (315 mg, 93 %). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 8.75 (br s, 4H, NH), 8.62 (br s, 24H, NH), 8.29 (br s, 256H, NH₃⁺), 7.85 (m, 48H, CH_{Ph}), 7.03 (br s, 8H, CH_{Ph}), 6.94 (m, 48H, CH_{Ph}), 6.59 (br s, 4H, CH_{Ph}), 3.94 (t, *J* = 7.0 Hz, 64H, OCH₂), 3.38 (br s, 56H, CH₂NH), 2.94 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 144H, CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.76 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 144H, CH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.63 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 56H, SCH₂CH₂NH), 2.54 (t, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 200H, Si(CH₂)₂CH₂S), 1.68 (br s, 64H, OCH₂CH₂), 1.56–1.48 (m, 200H, SiCH₂CH₂), 0.65–0.60 (m, 264H, SiCH₂). **¹³C {¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹³C HSQC, ¹H-¹³C HMBC): δ 165.8 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 165.6 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), 160.9 ((CH_{Ph})₂C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 159.7 (C_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 136.1 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 129.1 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 126.3 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), not detected (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}), 70.2 (OCH₂), from HSQC 39.5 (CH₂NH), 38.7 (CH₂NH₃⁺), 34.8 (Si^{0/1}(CH₂)₂CH₂S), 34.5 (Si²(CH₂)₂CH₂S), 30.5 (SCH₂CH₂NH), 27.8 (SCH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 23.8 (Si^{0/1}CH₂CH₂CH₂S), 23.7 (Si²CH₂CH₂CH₂S), 23.2 (OCH₂CH₂), 11.1 (SiCH₂(CH₂)₂S), 7.7 (O(CH₂)₂CH₂Si). **²⁹Si {¹H} NMR** (79 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ not detected or overlapped (Si⁰), 4.03 (Si²), 3.94 (Si¹). **MALDI-TOF MS** (DHB, Na⁺): *m/z* (avg. mass) calcd. for [C₇₉₂H₁₄₇₂N₁₀₀NaO₆₀S₁₀₀Si₃₃]⁺ 17512.7, found 17513.2 [M+Na]⁺.

G₂-6-6-A. Dendrimer G₂-6-6-A was prepared from 1.00 g (188 μmol) of G₁-6-N according to General procedure GP1. The product was purified by OSN using 3kDa membrane in DCM/MeOH mixture 1:1 and obtained as a yellow viscous substance (3.13 g, 98 %). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 6.95 (br s, 28H, NH), 6.90 (d, *J* = 2.2 Hz, 56H, CH_{Ph}), 6.52 (t, *J* = 2.2 Hz, 28H, CH_{Ph}), 5.77 (ddt, *J* = 16.4, 10.2, 8.1 Hz, 144H, CHCH₂), 4.90–4.85 (m, 288H, CHCH₂), 3.85 (t, 112H, *J* = 6.5 Hz, OCH₂), 3.58 (td, *J* = 6.8, 5.9 Hz, 56H, CH₂NH), 2.72 (t, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 56H, SCH₂CH₂NH), 2.53 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 56H, SCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), 1.80–1.72 (m, 112H, OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si), 1.60 (dt, *J* = 8.1, 1.1 Hz, 288H, SiCH₂CH), 1.59–1.54 (m, 56H, SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 0.68–0.60 (m, 168H, SiCH₂). **¹³C {¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃, ¹H-¹³C HSQC, ¹H-¹³C HMBC): δ 167.4 (HNCO), 160.4 (C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 136.5 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}), 134.2 (CHCH₂), 114.0 (CHCH₂), 105.6 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 104.6 (CH₂OC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 70.8 (OCH₂), 39.4 (CH₂NH), 35.6 (Si(CH₂)₂CH₂S), 31.7 (SCH₂CH₂NH), 24.4 (SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 23.9 (OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si¹), 23.5 (OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si²), 19.6 (SiCH₂CH), 11.8 (SiCH₂(CH₂)₂S), 8.4 (Si¹CH₂(CH₂)₂O), 7.6 (Si²CH₂(CH₂)₂O). **²⁹Si {¹H} NMR** (79 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 4.06 (Si¹), -0.12 (Si²), not detected or overlapped (Si⁰). **MALDI-TOF MS** (DCTB, Na⁺): *m/z* (avg. mass) calcd. for [C₉₃₆H₁₄₄₈N₂₈NaO₈₄S₂₈Si₅₇]⁺ 16959.3, found 16960.6 [M+Na]⁺.

G₂-6-6-N. Dendrimer G₂-6-6-N was prepared from 200 mg (11.8 μmol) of dendrimer G₂-6-6-A according to General procedure GP2. The product was purified by OSN using 3kDa membrane in MeOH followed by lyophilization and obtained as off-white powder (370 mg, 94 %). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 8.83 (br s, 28H, NH), 8.32 (br s, 432H, NH₃⁺), 7.04 (br s, 56H, CH_{Ph}), 6.57 (br s, 28H, CH_{Ph}), 3.93 (br s, 112H, OCH₂), overlapped with water (56H, CH₂NH), 2.95 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 298H, CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.77 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 298H, CH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.66 (br s, 56H, SCH₂CH₂NH), 2.55 (t, *J* = 7.0 Hz, 354H, Si(CH₂)₂CH₂S), 1.67 (br s, 112H, OCH₂CH₂), 1.56–1.48 (m, 354H, SiCH₂CH₂), 0.65–0.62 (m, 466H, SiCH₂). **¹³C {¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹³C HSQC, ¹H-¹³C HMBC): δ 165.6 (NHCO), 159.7 (C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 136.2 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}), 105.7 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}), 103.9 (CH_{Ph}), 70.4 (OCH₂), from HSQC 37.9 (CH₂NH), 38.7 (CH₂NH₃⁺), 35.0 (Si^{0/1}(CH₂)₂CH₂S), 34.5 (Si²(CH₂)₂CH₂S), 30.4 (SCH₂CH₂NH), 27.8 (SCH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 23.8 (SiCH₂CH₂), 23.3 (OCH₂CH₂), 11.2 (SiCH₂(CH₂)₂S), 7.8 (O(CH₂)₂CH₂Si). **²⁹Si {¹H} NMR** (79 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 4.01 (Si²), not detected or overlapped (Si^{0/1}). **MALDI-TOF MS** (DHB, Na⁺): *m/z* (avg. mass) calcd. for [C₁₂₁₈H₂₄₃₆N₁₆₉O₈₄S₁₆₉Si₅₇]⁺ 27814.9, calcd. for [C₁₂₁₈H₂₄₃₅N₁₆₉NaO₈₄S₁₆₉Si₅₇]⁺ 27836.8, found 27830.5 overlap of [M-3x(HSCH₂CH₂NH₂)+H]⁺ and [M-3x(HSCH₂CH₂NH₂)+Na]⁺.

3rd generation dendrimers

G₃-3-3-A. Dendrimer G₃-3-3-A was prepared from 450 mg (42.8 μmol) of G₂-3-3-N according to General procedure GP1. The product was purified by OSN using 3kDa membrane in DCM/MeOH mixture 1:1 and obtained as a brownish viscous substance (810 mg, 92 %). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 7.75 (m, 108H, CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}CONH), 7.19 (br s, 4H, NH), 7.11 (t, *J* = 5.5 Hz, 12H, NH), 6.93 (t, *J* = 5.5 Hz, 36H, NH), 6.86 (m, 108H, CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 5.78 (ddt, *J* = 16.5, 10.1, 8.1 Hz, 108H, CHCH₂), 4.92–4.85 (m, 216H, CHCH₂), 3.90 (t, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 104H, OCH₂), 3.57 (td, *J* = 6.6, 5.5 Hz, 104H, CH₂NH), 2.71 (t, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 104H, SCH₂CH₂NH), 2.51 (t, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 104H, SCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), 1.84–1.72 (m, 72H, OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si³), 1.76–1.69 (m, 32H, OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si^{1/2}), 1.61 (dt, *J* = 8.1, 1.1 Hz, 216H, SiCH₂CH), 1.57–1.53 (m, 104H, SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 0.71–0.61 (m, 208H, SiCH₂). **¹³C {¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃, ¹H-¹³C HSQC, ¹H-¹³C HMBC): δ 167.3 (HN^{0/1}CO), 167.2 (HN²CO), 161.8 (C_{q(Ph)}O^{0/1}CH₂), 161.6 (C_{q(Ph)}O²CH₂), 134.2 (CHCH₂), 129.04 (HN^{0/1}COC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}), 128.95 (HN²COC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}), 126.6 (HN^{0/1}COC_{q(Ph)}), 126.5 (HN²COC_{q(Ph)}), 114.3 (CH_{Ph}COCH₂), 114.0 (CHCH₂), 70.7 (O²CH₂), 70.6 (O^{0/1}CH₂), 39.4 (CH₂N^{0/1}H), 39.2 (CH₂N²H), 35.64 (Si^{0/1}(CH₂)₂CH₂S), 35.61 (Si²(CH₂)₂CH₂S), 31.9 (SCH₂CH₂N²H), 31.8 (SCH₂CH₂N^{0/1}H), 24.4 (SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 23.7 (O^{0/1}CH₂CH₂), 23.4 (O²CH₂CH₂), 19.6 (SiCH₂CH), 11.8 (SiCH₂(CH₂)₂S), 8.3 (O^{0/1}(CH₂)₂CH₂), 7.6 (O²(CH₂)₂CH₂). **²⁹Si {¹H} NMR** (79 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 4.04 (Si²), 4.03 (Si¹), not detected or overlapped (Si⁰), -0.11 (Si³). **MALDI-TOF MS** (DCTB, Na⁺): *m/z* (avg. mass) calcd. for [C₁₁₀₄H₁₆₃₃N₅₂O₁₀₄S₅₂Si₅₃]⁺ 20453.6, found 20456.8 [M+H]⁺.

G₃-3-3-3-N. Dendrimer G₃-3-3-3-N was prepared from 597 mg (29.2 μmol) of dendrimer G₃-3-3-3-A according to General procedure GP2. The product was purified by OSN using 3kDa membrane in MeOH followed by lyophilization and obtained as a white powder (946 mg, 99 %). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, **100 °C**, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 8.27 (br s, 52H, NH, 324H, NH₃⁺), 7.83 (m, 104H, CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}CONH), 6.93 (m, 104H, CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 4.00 (t, *J* = 6.3 Hz, 72H, OCH₂(CH₂)₂Si³), 3.97 (t, *J* = 6.3 Hz, 32H, OCH₂(CH₂)₂Si³), 3.43 (ddd, *J* = 8.2, 6.3, 5.8 Hz, 104H, CH₂NH), 2.98 (dd, *J* = 8.6, 6.2 Hz, 216H, CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.83 (dd, *J* = 8.6, 6.2 Hz, 216H, CH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.69 (dd, *J* = 8.2, 6.3 Hz, 104H, SCH₂CH₂NH), 2.58 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 216H, SCH₂(CH₂)₂Si³), 2.56 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 104H, SCH₂(CH₂)₂Si^{2/1}), 1.78–1.71 (m, 104H, OCH₂CH₂), 1.63–1.55 (m, 320H, SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 0.70–0.64 (m, 424H, SiCH₂). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 8.61 (br s, 52H, NH), 8.30 (br s, 324H, NH₃⁺), 7.84 (m, 104H, CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}CONH), 6.94 (m, 104H, CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 3.94 (t, *J* = 6.3 Hz, 104H, OCH₂), 3.41–3.35 overlapped with H₂O (m, 104H, CH₂NH), 2.93 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 216H, CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.75 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 216H, CH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.63 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 104H, SCH₂CH₂NH), 2.54 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 320H, SCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), 1.70–1.66 (m, 104H, OCH₂CH₂), 1.55–1.47 (m, 320H, SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 0.70–0.60 (m, 424H, SiCH₂). **¹³C {¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹³C HSQC, ¹H-¹³C HMBC): δ 165.6 (HNCO), 160.9 (C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 129.1 (HNCO C_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}), 126.3 (HNCO C_{q(Ph)}), 113.9 (CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 70.2 (OCH₂), from HSQC 39.6 (CH₂NH), 38.7 (CH₂NH₃⁺), 34.8 (CH₂S(CH₂)₂NH), 34.5 (CH₂S(CH₂)₂NH₃⁺), 30.5 (SCH₂CH₂NH), 27.8 (SCH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 23.8 (CH₂CH₂S(CH₂)₂NH), 23.7 (CH₂CH₂S(CH₂)₂NH₃⁺), 23.2 (OCH₂CH₂), 11.2, 11.1 (SiCH₂(CH₂)₂S), 7.7 (O(CH₂)₂CH₂). **²⁹Si {¹H} NMR** (79 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ overlapped or not detected (Si^{0/1}), 4.03 (Si³), 3.97 (Si²). **MALDI-TOF MS** (DHB, Na⁺): *m/z* (avg. mass) calcd. for [C₁₃₁₆H₂₃₇₄N₁₅₈O₁₀₄S₁₅₈Si₅₃]⁺ 28653.3, found 28651.3 [M-2x(HSCH₂CH₂NH₂)+Na]⁺.

G₃-3-3-6-A. Dendrimer G₂-3-3-6-A was prepared from 200 mg (19.0 μmol) of G₂-3-3-N according to General procedure GP1. The product was purified by OSN using 3kDa membrane in DCM/MeOH mixture 1:1 and obtained as a brownish amorphous solid (485 mg, 91 %). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 7.74 (m, 32H, HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 6.89 (d, *J* = 2.2 Hz, 36H, HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 6.88 (m, 32H, CH_{Ph}), 6.83 (br s, 52H, NH), 6.53 (t, *J* = 2.2 Hz, 36H, CH_{Ph}), 5.77 (ddt, *J* = 16.3, 9.9, 8.1 Hz, 216H, CHCH₂), 4.91–4.85 (m, 432H, CHCH₂), 3.92, 3.87 (2xt, *J* = 6.1 Hz, 176H, OCH₂), 3.58 (td, *J* = 6.5, 5.7 Hz, 104H, CH₂NH), 2.72 (t, *J* = 6.5 Hz, 104H, SCH₂CH₂NH), 2.53 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 104H, SCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), 1.81–1.74 (m, 176H, OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si), 1.61–1.57 (m, 104H, SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 1.60 (dt, *J* = 8.1, 1.1 Hz, 432H, SiCH₂CH), 0.69–0.63 (m, 280H, SiCH₂). **¹³C {¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃, ¹H-¹³C HSQC, ¹H-¹³C HMBC): δ 167.4 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 167.2 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), 161.7 ((CH_{Ph})₂C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 160.4 (C_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 136.5 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 134.2 (CHCH₂), 129.0 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 126.6 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), 114.3 (CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 114.0 (CHCH₂), 105.6 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 104.5 (CH₂OC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 70.8 (OCH₂(CH₂)₂Si³), 70.6 (OCH₂(CH₂)₂Si^{1/2}), 39.3 (CH₂NH), 35.6 (Si(CH₂)₂CH₂S), 31.8 (SCH₂CH₂NH), 24.4 (SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 23.7 (OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si^{1/2}), 23.4 (OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si³), 19.6 (SiCH₂CH), 11.8 (SiCH₂(CH₂)₂S), 8.3 (O(CH₂)₂CH₂Si^{1/2}), 7.62 (O(CH₂)₂CH₂Si³). **²⁹Si {¹H} NMR** (79 MHz, CDCl₃): δ not detected or overlapped (Si^{0/1}), 4.07 (Si²), -0.12 (Si³).

G₃-3-3-6-N. Dendrimer G₃-3-3-6-N was prepared from 160 mg (5.72 μmol) of dendrimer G₃-3-3-6-A according to General procedure GP2. The product was purified by OSN using 3kDa membrane in MeOH followed by lyophilization and obtained as an off-white powder (267 mg, 89 %). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 8.50 (br s, 52H, NH), 8.30 (br s, 648H, NH₃⁺), 7.85 (m, 32H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 7.06 (d, *J* = 2.2 Hz, 72H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 6.95 (m, 32H, CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 6.60 (t, *J* = 2.2 Hz, 36H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 4.00 (t, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 176H, OCH₂), 3.45 (td, *J* = 7.3, 5.6 Hz, 104H, CH₂NH), 3.00 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 432H, CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.85 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 432H, CH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.72 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 104H, CH₂CH₂NH), 2.60 (t, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 536H, SCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), 1.77–1.71 (m, 176H, OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si), 1.64–1.57 (m, 536H, SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 0.72–0.66 (m, 712H, SiCH₂). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 8.81 (br s, 36H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 8.66 (br s, 16H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), 8.33 (br s, 648H, NH₃⁺), 7.85 (br s, 32H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 7.03 (s, 72H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 6.93 (br s, 32H, CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 6.57 (br s, 36H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 3.94 (br s, 176H, OCH₂), overlapped with water (CH₂NH), 2.94 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 432H, CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.76 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 432H, CH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.63 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 104H, CH₂CH₂NH), 2.55 (t, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 536H, SCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), 1.67 (br s, 176H, OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si), 1.56–1.48 (m, 536H, SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 0.65–0.61 (m, 712H, SiCH₂). **¹³C {¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹³C HSQC, ¹H-¹³C HMBC): δ 165.6 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), not detected (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), 160.9 ((CH_{Ph})₂C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 159.6 (C_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 136.2 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 129.0 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 126.2 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), 113.8 (CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 105.7 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 103.9 (OC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}O), 70.4 (OCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), from HSQC 39.7 (CH₂NH), 38.7 (CH₂NH₃⁺), 34.8 (CH₂S(CH₂)₂NH), 34.5 (CH₂S(CH₂)₂NH₃⁺), 30.4 (CH₂CH₂NH), 27.8 (CH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 23.7 (CH₂CH₂S(CH₂)₂NH), 23.3 (CH₂CH₂O), 11.1 (SiCH₂(CH₂)₂S), 7.8 (SiCH₂(CH₂)₂O). **²⁹Si {¹H} NMR** (79 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 4.01 (Si³), not detected or overlapped (Si^{0/1/2}).

G₃-3-6-3-A. Dendrimer G₃-3-6-3-A was prepared from 100 mg (5.85 μmol) of G₂-3-6-N according to General procedure GP1. The product was purified by OSN using 3kDa membrane in DCM/MeOH mixture, starting at 1:1 ratio and gradually increasing the polarity up to 1:2 so as to maintain the homogeneity of the solution, and obtained as a brownish amorphous solid (207 mg, 95 %). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 7.76 (m, 152H, HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 7.10 (br s, 88H, NH), 6.98 (br s, 24H, HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 6.84 (m, 152H, CH_{Ph}), 6.53 (br s, 12H, CH_{Ph}), 5.77 (ddt, *J* = 16.4, 10.1, 8.1 Hz, 216H, CHCH₂), 4.91–4.84 (m, 432H, CHCH₂), 3.91 (2xt, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 200H, OCH₂), 3.56 (td, *J* = 6.8, 5.7 Hz, 176H, CH₂NH), 2.70 (t, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 176H, SCH₂CH₂NH), 2.50 (t, *J* = 6.9 Hz, 176H, SCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), 1.83–1.76 (m, 152H, OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si^{0/3}), 1.67 (br s, 48H, OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si²), 1.60 (dt, *J* = 8.1, 1.1 Hz, 432H, SiCH₂CH), 1.59–1.52 (m, 176H, SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 0.70–0.56 (m, 152H, Si^{0/3}CH₂(CH₂)₂O), 0.63–0.59 (m, 176H, SiCH₂(CH₂)₂S, 48H, Si²CH₂(CH₂)₂O). **¹³C {¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃, ¹H-¹³C HSQC, ¹H-¹³C HMBC): δ 167.6 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 167.2 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), 161.8 ((CH_{Ph})₂C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 160.3 (C_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 136.6 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 134.2 (CHCH₂), 129.0 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 126.5 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), 114.3 (CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 114.0 (CHCH₂), 105.8 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 104.6 (CH₂OC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 70.8 (OCH₂(CH₂)₂Si²), 70.7 (OCH₂(CH₂)₂Si^{1/3}), 39.4 (CH₂NH), 35.6 (Si(CH₂)₂CH₂S), 31.8 (SCH₂CH₂NH), 24.4 (SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 23.8 (OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si²), 23.4 (OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si^{1/3}), 19.6 (SiCH₂CH), 11.8 (SiCH₂(CH₂)₂S), 8.3 (O(CH₂)₂CH₂Si²), 7.6 (O(CH₂)₂CH₂Si^{1/3}). **²⁹Si {¹H} NMR** (79 MHz, CDCl₃): δ not detected or overlapped (Si^{0/1}), 4.02 (Si²), -0.11 (Si³).

G₃-3-6-3-N. Dendrimer G₃-3-6-3-N was prepared from 150 mg (4.06 μmol) of dendrimer G₃-3-6-3-A according to General procedure GP2. The product was purified by OSN using 3kDa membrane in MeOH followed by lyophilization and obtained as an off-white powder (244 mg, 97 %). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, 100 °C, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 8.32 (br s, 736H, NH, NH₃⁺), 7.85 (m, 152H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 7.03 (s, 24H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 6.93 (m, 152H, CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 6.59 (s, 12H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 3.99 (t, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 200H, OCH₂), (td, *J* = 7.3, 5.8 Hz, 176H, CH₂NH), 2.99 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 432H, CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.84 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 432H, CH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.69 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 176H, CH₂CH₂NH), 2.58 (t, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 608H, SCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), 1.77–1.73 (m, 200H, OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si), 1.62–1.55 (m, 608H, SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 0.70–0.64 (m, 808H, SiCH₂). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 8.72 (br s, 12H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 8.64 (br s, 76H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), 8.32 (br s, 648H, NH₃⁺), 7.85 (m, 152H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 7.03 (s, 24H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 6.93 (m, 152H, CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 6.58 (s, 12H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 3.93 (br s, 200H, OCH₂), overlapped with water (br s, 176H, CH₂NH), 2.94 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 432H, CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.76 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 432H, CH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.62 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 176H, CH₂CH₂NH), 2.54 (t, *J* = 7.0 Hz, 608H, SCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), 1.67 (br s, 200H, OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si), 1.53–1.49 (m, 608H, SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 0.64–0.59 (m, 808H, SiCH₂). ¹³C {¹H} NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹³C HSQC, ¹H-¹³C HMBC): δ not detected (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 165.6 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), 160.9 ((CH_{Ph})₂C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 159.6 (C_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), not detected (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 129.1 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 126.3 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), 113.8 (CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), from HSQC at 100 °C 105.4 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), not detected (OC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}O), 70.2 (OCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), from HSQC 39.6 (CH₂NHCO), 38.7 (CH₂NH₃⁺), 34.8 (CH₂S(CH₂)₂NH), 34.5 (CH₂S(CH₂)₂NH₃⁺), 30.5 (CH₂CH₂NH), 27.8 (CH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 23.8 (CH₂CH₂S(CH₂)₂NH), 23.2 (CH₂CH₂O), 11.1 (SiCH₂(CH₂)₂S), 7.7 (SiCH₂(CH₂)₂O). ²⁹Si {¹H} NMR (79 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 4.02 (Si³), 3.93 (Si²), not detected or overlapped (Si^{0/1}).

G₃-3-6-6-A. Dendrimer G₃-3-6-6-A was prepared from 206 mg (12.0 μmol) of G₂-3-6-N according to General procedure GP1. The product was purified by OSN using 3kDa membrane in DCM/MeOH mixture 1:1 and obtained as a brownish amorphous solid (622 mg, 99 %). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 7.75 (m, 8H, HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 6.99–6.89 (m, 88H, NH, 168H, HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 8H, HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 6.52 (t, *J* = 2.2 Hz, 84H, CH_{Ph}), 5.76 (ddt, *J* = 16.7, 10.1, 8.1 Hz, 432H, CHCH₂), 4.90–4.84 (m, 864H, CHCH₂), 3.85 (t, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 344H, OCH₂), 3.56 (td, *J* = 6.8, 5.7 Hz, 176H, CH₂NH), 2.71 (t, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 176H, SCH₂CH₂NH), 2.52 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 176H, SCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), 1.79–1.71 (m, 344H, OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si), 1.59 (dt, *J* = 8.1, 1.1 Hz, 864H, SiCH₂CH), 1.60–1.58 (m, 176H, SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 0.67–0.63 (m, 520H, SiCH₂). ¹³C {¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃, ¹H-¹³C HSQC, ¹H-¹³C HMBC): δ 167.4 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), not detected (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), from HMB 161.7 ((CH_{Ph})₂C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 160.3 (C_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 136.5 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 134.2 (CHCH₂), 128.9 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 126.5 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), 114.3 (CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 114.0 (CHCH₂), 105.5 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 104.6 (CH₂OC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 70.8 (OCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), 39.4 (CH₂NH), 35.6 (Si(CH₂)₂CH₂S), 31.7 (SCH₂CH₂NH), 24.4 (SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 23.8 (OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si¹), 23.4 (OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si^{2/3}), 19.6 (SiCH₂CH), 11.8 (SiCH₂(CH₂)₂S), 8.4 (O(CH₂)₂CH₂Si¹), 7.6 (O(CH₂)₂CH₂Si^{2/3}). ²⁹Si {¹H} NMR (79 MHz, CDCl₃): δ not detected or overlapped (Si^{0/1}), 4.06 (Si²), –0.13 (Si³).

G₃-3-6-6-N. Dendrimer G₃-3-6-6-N was prepared from 198 mg (3.81 μmol) of dendrimer G₃-3-6-6-A according to General procedure GP2. The product was purified by OSN using 3kDa membrane in MeOH followed by lyophilization and obtained as an off-white powder (329 mg, 85 %). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, 100 °C, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 8.55 (s, 88H, NH), 8.34 (br s, 1296H, NH₃⁺), 7.83 (m, 8H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 7.06 (s, 168H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 6.95 (m, 8H, CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 6.59 (s, 84H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 3.99 (t, *J* = 6.5 Hz, 344H, OCH₂), 3.46–3.44 (m, 176H, CH₂NH), 3.01 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 864H, CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.86 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 864H, CH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.73 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 176H, CH₂CH₂NH), 2.60 (t, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 1040H, SCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), 1.78–1.72 (m, 344H, OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si), 1.64–1.56 (m, 1040H, SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 0.72–0.66 (m, 1384H, SiCH₂). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 8.88 (br s, 88H, NH), 8.35 (br s, 1296H, NH₃⁺), 7.82 (m, 8H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 7.04 (s, 168H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 6.93 (m, 8H, CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 6.56 (s, 84H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 3.93 (br s, 344H, OCH₂), overlapped with water (br s, 176H, CH₂NH), 2.94 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 864H, CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.76 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 864H, CH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.63 (br s, 176H, CH₂CH₂NH), 2.54 (t, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 1040H, SCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), 1.69 (br s, 344H, OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si), 1.51 (br s, 1040H, SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 0.63–0.60 (m, 1384H, SiCH₂). ¹³C {¹H} NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹³C HSQC, ¹H-¹³C HMBC): δ 165.6 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), not detected (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), not detected ((CH_{Ph})₂C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 159.6 (C_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 136.1 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), from HSQC 130.1 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), not detected (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), from HSQC 114.0 (CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 105.6 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 103.9 (OC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}O), 70.4 (OCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), from HSQC 39.7 (CH₂NH), 38.9 (CH₂NH₃⁺), 34.9 (CH₂S(CH₂)₂NH), 34.5 (CH₂S(CH₂)₂NH₃⁺), 30.4 (CH₂CH₂NH), 27.8 (CH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 23.7 (CH₂CH₂S(CH₂)₂NH), 23.3 (CH₂CH₂O), 11.2 (SiCH₂(CH₂)₂S), 7.8 (SiCH₂(CH₂)₂O). ²⁹Si {¹H} NMR (79 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 4.00 (Si³), not detected or overlapped (Si^{0/1/2}).

G₃-6-3-3-A. Dendrimer G₃-6-3-3-A was prepared from 193 mg (9.59 μmol) of G₂-6-3-N according to General procedure GP1. The product was purified by OSN using 3kDa membrane in DCM/MeOH mixture 2:3 and obtained as a yellowish foam (359 mg, 93 %). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 7.76 (m, 192H, HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 7.36 (br s, 16H, NH), 7.10 (br s, 72H, NH), 6.98 (br s, 8H, HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 6.84 (m, 192H, HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 6.53 (br s, 4H, CH₂OC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 5.77 (ddt, *J* = 16.4, 10.0, 8.1 Hz, 216H, CHCH₂), 4.91–4.84 (m, 432H, CHCH₂), 3.89 (t, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 208H, OCH₂), 3.56 (td, *J* = 6.8, 5.7 Hz, 200H, CH₂NH), 2.70 (t, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 200H, SCH₂CH₂NH), 2.51 (t, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 200H, SCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), 1.83–1.74 (m, 208H, OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si), 1.60 (dt, *J* = 8.1, 1.1 Hz, 432H, SiCH₂CH), 1.59–1.54 (m, 200H, SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 0.70–0.66 (m, 192H, (O(CH₂)₂CH₂Si)^{2/3}), 0.62–0.60 (m, 216H, SiCH₂(CH₂)₂S, (O(CH₂)₂CH₂Si)¹). **¹³C {¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃, ¹H-¹³C HSQC, ¹H-¹³C HMBC): δ 167.3 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 167.2 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), 161.8, 161.7 ((CH_{Ph})₂C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), not detected (C_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), not detected (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 134.2 (CHCH₂), 129.1, 129.0 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 126.6, 126.5 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), 114.3 (CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 114.0 (CHCH₂), not detected (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), not detected (CH₂OC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 70.7 (OCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), 39.4 (CH₂NH), 35.7 (Si(CH₂)₂CH₂S), 31.9 (SCH₂CH₂NH), 24.4 (SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 23.4 (OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si), 19.6 (SiCH₂CH), 11.6 (SiCH₂(CH₂)₂S), 8.3 (O(CH₂)₂CH₂Si¹), 7.6 (O(CH₂)₂CH₂Si^{2/3}). **²⁹Si {¹H} NMR** (79 MHz, CDCl₃): δ not detected (Si⁰), 4.03 (Si²), 4.00 (Si¹), –0.11 (Si³).

G₃-6-3-3-N. Dendrimer G₃-6-3-3-N was prepared from 208 mg (5.20 μmol) of dendrimer G₃-6-3-3-A according to General procedure GP2. The product was purified by OSN using 3kDa membrane in MeOH followed by lyophilization and obtained as a white powder (290 mg, 86 %). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, 100 °C, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 8.47 (br s, 4H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 8.30 (br s, 96H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂, 648H, NH₃Cl), 7.85 (m, 192H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 7.05 (8H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 6.93 (m, 192H, CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 6.63 (4H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 3.99, 3.95 (2xt, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 208H, OCH₂), 3.44 (td, *J* = 7.3, 5.8 Hz, 200H, CH₂NHCO), 2.99 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 432H, CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.84 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 432H, CH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.70 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 200H, CH₂CH₂NH), 2.58 (t, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 632H, SCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), 1.78–1.72 (m, 208H, OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si), 1.63–1.55 (m, 632H, SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 0.70–0.64 (m, 840H, SiCH₂). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 8.79 (br s, 4H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 8.64 (br s, 96H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), 8.31 (br s, 648H, NH₃Cl), 7.85 (m, 192H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), not detected (8H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 6.93 (m, 192H, CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), not detected (4H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 3.93 (br s, 208H, OCH₂), overlapped with water (CH₂NHCO), 2.94 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 432H, CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.76 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 432H, CH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.63 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 200H, CH₂CH₂NH), 2.54 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 632H, SCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), 1.67 (br s, 208H, OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si), 1.55–1.47 (m, 632H, SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 0.64–0.60 (m, 840H, SiCH₂). **¹³C {¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹³C HSQC, ¹H-¹³C HMBC): δ 165.6 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), not detected (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 160.9 ((CH_{Ph})₂C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), not detected (C_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), not detected (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 129.1 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 126.3 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), 113.8 (CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), not detected (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), not detected (OC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}O), 70.2 (OCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), from HSQC 39.4 (CH₂NH), 38.7 (CH₂NH₃⁺), 34.8 (CH₂S(CH₂)₂NH), 34.5 (CH₂S(CH₂)₂NH₃⁺), 30.5 (CH₂CH₂NH), 27.8 (CH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 23.7 (CH₂CH₂S(CH₂)₂NH), 23.2 (CH₂CH₂OC_{q(Ph)}), 11.1 (SiCH₂(CH₂)₂S), 7.7 (SiCH₂(CH₂)₂O). **²⁹Si {¹H} NMR** (79 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 4.02 (Si³), 3.96 (Si²), not detected or overlapped (Si^{0/1}).

G₃-6-3-6-A. Dendrimer G₃-6-3-6-A was prepared from 121 mg (6.02 μmol) of G₂-6-3-N according to General procedure GP1. The product was purified by OSN using 3kDa membrane in DCM/MeOH mixture 1:1 and obtained as a yellowish amorphous substance (266 mg, 80 %). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 7.74 (m, 48H, HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 7.09 (br s, 24H, NH), 6.99 (br s, 76H, NH), 6.91 (d, *J* = 2.2 Hz, 152H, HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 6.84 (m, 48H, HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 6.52 (t, *J* = 2.2 Hz, 76H, CH₂OC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 5.76 (ddt, *J* = 16.7, 10.1, 8.1 Hz, 432H, CHCH₂), 4.90–4.84 (m, 864H, CHCH₂), 3.88, 3.85 (2xt, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 352H, OCH₂), 3.57 (td, *J* = 6.8, 5.7 Hz, 200H, CH₂NH), 2.71 (t, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 200H, SCH₂CH₂NH), 2.53 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 200H, SCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), 1.79–1.72 (m, 352H, OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si), 1.59 (dt, *J* = 8.1, 1.1 Hz, 864H, SiCH₂CH), 1.59–1.52 (m, 200H, SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 0.67–0.63 (m, 552H, SiCH₂). ¹³C {¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃, ¹H-¹³C HSQC, ¹H-¹³C HMBC): δ 167.4 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 167.2 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), 161.7 ((CH_{Ph})₂C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 160.4 (C_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 136.5 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 134.2 (CHCH₂), 129.1 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 126.6 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), 114.3 (CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 114.0 (CHCH₂), 105.6 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 104.6 (CH₂OC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 70.8 (OCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), 39.4 (CH₂NH), 35.6 (Si(CH₂)₂CH₂S), 31.8 (SCH₂CH₂NH), 24.4 (SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 23.8 (OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si²), 23.4 (OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si^{1/3}), 19.6 (SiCH₂CH), 11.8 (SiCH₂(CH₂)₂S), 8.4 (O(CH₂)₂CH₂Si¹), 7.6 (O(CH₂)₂CH₂Si^{2/3}). ²⁹Si {¹H} NMR (79 MHz, CDCl₃): δ not detected or overlapped (Si^{0/1}), 4.07 (Si²), -0.12 (Si³).

G₃-6-3-6-N. Dendrimer G₃-6-3-6-N was prepared from 191 mg (3.47 μmol) of dendrimer G₃-6-3-6-A according to General procedure GP2. The product was purified by OSN using 3kDa membrane in MeOH followed by lyophilization and obtained as an off-white powder (303 mg, 83 %). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, 100 °C, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 8.53 (br s, 24H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), 8.33 (br s, 76H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 7.87 (br s, 48H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 7.06 (br s, 152H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 6.94 (br s, 48H, CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 6.59 (br s, 76H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 3.99 (t, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 352H, OCH₂), 3.45 (br s, 200H, CH₂NH), 3.01 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 864H, CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.85 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 864H, CH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.72 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 200H, CH₂CH₂NH), 2.59 (t, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 864H, SCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), 1.74–1.72 (m, 352H, OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si), 1.64–1.56 (m, 1064H, SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 0.71–0.67 (m, 1416H, SiCH₂). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 8.84 (br s, 24H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), 8.35 (br s, 76H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 7.86 (br s, 48H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 7.05 (br s, 152H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 6.94 (br s, 48H, CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 6.57 (br s, 76H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 3.94 (br s, 352H, OCH₂), overlapped with water (br s, 200H, CH₂NH), 2.95 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 864H, CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.78 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 864H, CH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.64 (br s, 200H, CH₂CH₂NH), 2.55 (t, *J* = 7.0 Hz, 864H, SCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), 1.67 (br s, 352H, OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si), 1.52 (br s, 1064H, SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 0.62 (m, 1416H, SiCH₂). ¹³C {¹H} NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹³C HSQC, ¹H-¹³C HMBC): δ not detected (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), 165.6 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), not detected ((CH_{Ph})₂C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 159.6 (C_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 136.2 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 129.1 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 126.3 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), 113.8 (CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 105.7 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 103.9 (OC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}O), 70.4 (OCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), from HSQC 39.6 (CH₂NH), 38.7 (CH₂NH₃⁺), 34.9 (CH₂S(CH₂)₂NH), 34.5 (CH₂S(CH₂)₂NH₃⁺), 30.4 (CH₂CH₂NH), 27.8 (CH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 23.7 (CH₂CH₂S(CH₂)₂NH), 23.3 (CH₂CH₂O), 11.2

(SiCH₂(CH₂)₂S), 7.8 (SiCH₂(CH₂)₂O). ²⁹Si {¹H} NMR (79 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 4.01 (Si³), not detected or overlapped (Si^{0/1/2}).

G₃-6-6-3-A. Dendrimer G₃-6-6-3-A was prepared from 125 mg (3.76 μmol) of G₂-6-6-N according to General procedure GP1. The product was purified by OSN using 3kDa membrane in DCM/MeOH mixture, starting at 1:1 ratio and gradually increasing the polarity up to 3:5 so as to maintain the homogeneity of the solution, and obtained as brownish foam (235 mg, 85 %). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 7.76 (m, 288H, HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 7.37 (br s, 152H, NH), 7.00 (br s, 56H, HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 6.81 (m, 288H, HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 6.52 (br s, 28H, CH₂OC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 5.76 (ddt, *J* = 16.7, 10.1, 8.1 Hz, 432H, CHCH₂), 4.89–4.83 (m, 864H, CHCH₂), 3.87 (t, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 400H, OCH₂), 3.54 (td, *J* = 6.7, 5.7 Hz, 344H, CH₂N), 2.69 (t, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 344H, SCH₂CH₂NH), 2.49 (t, *J* = 6.9 Hz, 344H, SCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), 1.81–1.73 (m, 400H, OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si), 1.59 (dt, *J* = 8.1, 1.1 Hz, 864H, SiCH₂CH), 1.59–1.52 (m, 344H, SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 0.68–0.59 (m, 744H, SiCH₂). ¹³C {¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃, ¹H-¹³C HSQC, ¹H-¹³C HMBC): δ 167.3 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), HNCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂, 161.7 ((CH_{Ph})₂C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 160.3 (C_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 136.5 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 134.2 (CHCH₂), 129.1 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 126.5 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), 114.3 (CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 114.0 (CHCH₂), 105.8 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 104.7 (CH₂OC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 70.6 (OCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), 39.7 (CH₂NH), 35.7 (Si(CH₂)₂CH₂S), 31.8 (SCH₂CH₂NH), 24.4 (SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 23.8 (OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si^{1/2}), 23.4 (OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si³), 19.6 (SiCH₂CH), 11.8 (SiCH₂(CH₂)₂S), 8.3 (O(CH₂)₂CH₂Si^{1/2}), 7.6 (O(CH₂)₂CH₂Si³). ²⁹Si {¹H} NMR (79 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 4.11 (Si¹), 3.99 (Si²), -0.12 (Si³), not detected or overlapped (Si⁰).

G₃-6-6-3-N. Dendrimer G₃-6-6-3-N was prepared from 187 mg (2.56 μmol) of dendrimer G₃-6-6-3-A according to General procedure GP2. The product was purified by OSN using 3kDa membrane in MeOH followed by lyophilization and obtained as off-white powder (298 mg, 95 %). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, 100 °C, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 8.51 (br s, 28H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 8.33 (br s, 144H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂, 1296H, NH₃⁺), 7.86 (m, 288H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 7.04 (s, 56H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 6.92 (m, 288H, CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 6.59 (28H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 3.97 (br s, 400H, OCH₂), 3.44 (dt, *J* = 7.0, 6.5 Hz, 344H, CH₂NH), 3.00 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 864H, CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.85 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 864H, CH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.69 (t, *J* = 7.0 Hz, 344H, CH₂CH₂NH), 2.58 (t, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 1208H, SCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), 1.73 (br s, 400H, OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si), 1.62–1.55 (m, 1208H, SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 0.70–0.63 (m, 1608H, SiCH₂). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 8.65 (br s, 28H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 144H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂, 8.34 (s, 1296H, NH₃⁺), 7.86 (m, 288H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 6.91 (br s, 56H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 288H, CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 6.58 (28H, NHCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 3.91 (br s, 400H, OCH₂), overlapped with water (CH₂NH), 2.94 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 864H, CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.77 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 864H, CH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.62 (br s, 344H, CH₂CH₂NH), 2.54 (br s, 1208H, SCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), 1.63 (br s, 400H, OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si), 1.50 (br s, 1208H, SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 0.60 (br s, 1608H, SiCH₂). ¹³C {¹H} NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹³C HSQC, ¹H-¹³C HMBC): δ 165.6 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), not detected (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 160.9 ((CH_{Ph})₂C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), 159.6 (C_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), not detected (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), 129.1 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}), 126.3 (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}(CH_{Ph})₂), 113.8 (CH_{Ph}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}OCH₂), not detected (HNCOC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}), not detected (OC_{q(Ph)}CH_{Ph}C_{q(Ph)}O), 70.2 (OCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), from HSQC 39.5

(CH₂NHCO), 38.7 (CH₂NH₃⁺), 34.9 (CH₂S(CH₂)₂NH), 34.5 (CH₂S(CH₂)₂NH₃⁺), 30.7 (CH₂CH₂NH), 27.8 (CH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 23.7 (CH₂CH₂S(CH₂)₂NH), 23.2 (CH₂CH₂O), 11.1 (SiCH₂(CH₂)₂S), 7.7 (SiCH₂(CH₂)₂O). ²⁹Si {¹H} NMR (79 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 4.02 (Si³), 3.91 (Si²), not detected or overlapped (Si^{0/1}).

G₃-6-6-6-A. Dendrimer G₃-6-6-6-A was prepared from 800 mg (24.0 μmol) of G₂-6-6-N according to General procedure GP1. The product was purified by OSN using 3kDa membrane in DCM/MeOH mixture 4:3 and obtained as a brownish viscous substance (2.39 g, 96 %). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 7.32 (br s, 172H, NH), 6.92 (br s, 344H, CH_{Ph}), 6.50 (br s, 172H, CH_{Ph}), 5.74 (ddt, *J* = 17.4, 10.2, 8.2 Hz, 824H, CHCH₂), 4.88–4.83 (m, 1728H, CHCH₂), 3.88–3.80 (m, 688H, OCH₂), 3.58–3.55 (m, 344H, CH₂NH), 2.70 (t, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 344H, SCH₂CH₂NH), 2.53–2.50 (m, 344H, SCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), 1.75–1.67 (m, 688H, OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si), 1.57 (dt, *J* = 8.2, 1.1 Hz, 1728H, SiCH₂CH), 1.58–1.56 (m, 344H, SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 0.67–0.59 (m, 1030H, SiCH₂). ¹³C {¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃, ¹H-¹³C HSQC, ¹H-¹³C HMBC): δ 167.4 (HNCO), 160.3 (CH_{Ph}C_q(Ph)OCH₂), 136.4 (HNCOC_q(Ph)CH_{Ph}C_q(Ph)), 134.2 (CHCH₂), 114.0 (CHCH₂), 105.6 (HNCOC_q(Ph)CH_{Ph}C_q(Ph)), 104.6 (CH₂OC_q(Ph)CH_{Ph}C_q(Ph)OCH₂), 70.8 (OCH₂(CH₂)₂Si), 39.8 (CH₂NH), 35.7 (Si(CH₂)₂CH₂S), 31.7 (SCH₂CH₂NH), 24.4 (SiCH₂CH₂CH₂S), 23.8 (OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si^{1/2}), 23.4 (OCH₂CH₂CH₂Si³), 19.6 (SiCH₂CH), 11.8 (SiCH₂(CH₂)₂S), 8.4 (O(CH₂)₂CH₂Si^{1/2}), 7.6 (O(CH₂)₂CH₂Si³). ²⁹Si {¹H} NMR (79 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 4.03 (Si²), -0.14 (Si³), not detected or overlapped (Si^{0/1}).

G₃-6-6-6-N. Dendrimer G₃-6-6-6-N was prepared from 132 mg (1.28 μmol) of dendrimer G₃-6-6-6-A according to General procedure GP2. The product was purified by OSN using 3kDa membrane in MeOH followed by lyophilization and obtained as off-white powder (240 mg, 93 %). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, **100** °C, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 8.57 (br s, 172H, NH), 8.35 (br s, 2592H, NH₃⁺), 7.06 (br s, 344H, CH_{Ph}), 6.58 (br s, 172H, CH_{Ph}), 3.98 (br s, 688H, OCH₂), 3.46 (344H, CH₂NH), 3.04–3.01 (m, 1728H, CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.88 (t, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 1728H, CH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.73 (br s, 344H, SCH₂CH₂NH), 2.60 (t, *J* = 7.0 Hz, 2072H, Si(CH₂)₂CH₂S), 1.72 (br s, 688H, OCH₂CH₂), 1.64–1.56 (m, 2072H, SiCH₂CH₂), 0.65–0.62 (m, 2760H, SiCH₂). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 8.38 (br s, 172H, NH, 2592H, NH₃⁺), 7.03 (br s, 344H, CH_{Ph}), 6.56 (br s, 172H, CH_{Ph}), 3.92 (br s, 688H, OCH₂), overlapped with water (CH₂NH), 2.96 (br s, 1728H, CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.79 (br s, 1728H, CH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.55 (br s, 344H, SCH₂CH₂NH, 2072H, Si(CH₂)₂CH₂S), 1.64 (br s, 688H, OCH₂CH₂), 1.51 (m, 2072H, SiCH₂CH₂), 0.62 (br s, 2760H, SiCH₂). ¹³C {¹H} NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ¹H-¹³C HSQC, ¹H-¹³C HMBC): δ 165.6 (NHCO), 159.7 (C_q(Ph)OCH₂), not detected (HNCOC_q(Ph)), not detected (HNCOC_q(Ph)CH_{Ph}), not detected (CH_{Ph}), from HSQC 70.4 (OCH₂), not detected (CH₂NH), 38.8 (CH₂NH₃⁺), 34.6 (Si(CH₂)₂CH₂S), not detected (SCH₂CH₂NH), 27.8 (SCH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 23.7 (SiCH₂CH₂), 23.3 (OCH₂CH₂), 11.2 (SiCH₂(CH₂)₂S), 7.8 (O(CH₂)₂CH₂Si). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CD₃OD, ¹H-¹H COSY): δ 7.08 (br s, 344H, CH_{Ph}), 6.64 (br s, 172H, CH_{Ph}), 3.98 (br s, 688H, OCH₂), 3.58 (344H, CH₂NH), 3.22–3.17 (m, 1728H, CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.94–2.90 (m, 1728H, CH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 2.84–2.80 (m, 344H, SCH₂CH₂NH), 2.65–2.61 (m, 2072H, Si(CH₂)₂CH₂S), 1.76 (br s, 688H, OCH₂CH₂), 1.64 (m, 2072H, SiCH₂CH₂), 0.73 (br s, 2760H, SiCH₂). ¹³C {¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CD₃OD, ¹H-¹³C HSQC, ¹H-¹³C HMBC): δ 169.3 (NHCO), 161.7 (C_q(Ph)OCH₂), 137.4 (HNCOC_q(Ph)), 107.1 (HNCOC_q(Ph)CH_{Ph}), from HSQC 105.9 (CH_{Ph}), 72.3 (OCH₂), 40.5 (CH₂NH₃⁺), 40.3 (CH₂NH), 36.5 (Si(CH₂)₂CH₂S), 32.3 (SCH₂CH₂NH), 29.8 (SCH₂CH₂NH₃⁺), 25.5 (SiCH₂CH₂),

25.0 (OCH₂CH₂), 12.7 (SiCH₂(CH₂)₂S), 9.4 (O(CH₂)₂CH₂Si). ²⁹Si {¹H} NMR (79 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 3.94 (Si³), not detected or overlapped (Si^{0/1/2}).

2. MALDI-TOF and ESI-QTOF MS analysis

The smallest polyallyl dendrimer G₁-3-A and both 1st generation polycationic dendrimers G₁-3-N and G₁-6-N were characterized by ESI-QTOF HRMS in addition to MALDI-TOF MS. Molar masses of the ammonium dendrimers G₁-3-N and G₁-6-N are at the upper bound of the measurable range for conventional ESI-QTOF HRMS (3114.2 and 5310.9 g/mol, resp.). As such, direct observation of their molecular peaks was unsuccessful. However, as reported for other dendritic polyelectrolytes,¹ the easily ionizable character of the structures enables their observation as a Gauss-like distribution of polycations. During ionization, the molecules lost all chlorides either in the form of HCl or as Cl⁻ ions, leaving part of the amino groups protonated. Thus, we could observe ions of a general structure [M-xHCl+yH]^{y+}, where x = number of PG and y = charge of the particular ion. The ionization optimum was around 25 % for both G₁ ammonium dendrimers, i.e., the most abundant ions were from M²⁺ to M⁴⁺ for G₁-3-N, and from M⁴⁺ to M⁷⁺ for G₁-6-N.

Regarding the dendritic purity of the prepared compounds, several defective structures were observed in mass spectra. Structures resulting from incomplete TEC reaction, missing one or two ammonium linkers, accompanied all ions of non-defective dendrimers in nearly constant ratios, which were in agreement with a statistical character of such defects. Assuming similar ionizabilities of the defective structures (possessing nearly the same number of ionizable ammonium PGs and similar molecular weight), it is possible to calculate the conversion ξ of the TEC reaction and thus the defectiveness of the surface of ammonium dendrimers (1- ξ) from observed intensities of non-defective and defective ions according to Eq. 2.

$$\xi = \frac{n}{n + \frac{I_{D1}}{I_{D0}}} \quad (2)$$

where n represents the number of reacting groups per molecule and I_{Dx} stands for the peak intensity of the structure with x defects. It has to be noted that the actual quantity of unreacted groups can be lower due to a plausible fragmentation pathway, reverse elimination on a thioether bond, which would generate a thiol and the observed allyl-containing fragment.

Only the smallest G₂ ammonium dendrimer with 36 PGs gave useful ESI-QTOF HRMS data; larger ammonium dendrimers ionized in a wide distribution of differently charged ions, which, together with broadening of their isotopic multiplets at higher masses and increasing probability of defects and fragmentation, had a detrimental effect on the S/N ratio. The rest of the G₂ structures were thus analyzed only by MALDI-TOF MS, mostly in a linear mode, while most G₃ dendrimers were too large even for this ionization method. Again, polyallyl dendrimers showed complete conversion of the amidic coupling, while for polyammonium dendrimers we observed the presence of structures missing 1-3 ammonium linkers, which corresponded to ca. 98% conversion of TEC leaving 2% of unreacted allyl groups. In any case, the above remarks on the possible fragmentation of thioesters apply also to higher generations.

Figure S1: ESI⁺ QTOF mass spectrum of G₀-N

Figure S2: ESI⁺ QTOF mass spectrum of MeO-AB₃

Figure S3: ESI⁻ QTOF mass spectrum of AB₃

Figure S4: ESI⁺ QTOF mass spectrum of BtO-AB₃

Figure S5. ESI⁺ QTOF mass spectrum of G₁-3-A

Figure S6. MALDI-TOF mass spectrum (DCTB/Na⁺; reflectron mode) of G₁-3-A

Figure S7. ESI⁺ QTOF mass spectrum of G₁-3-N

Figure S8. MALDI-TOF mass spectrum (DHB/Na⁺; reflectron mode) of G₁-3-N

Figure S9. MALDI-TOF mass spectrum (DHB/Na⁺; reflectron mode) of G₁-6-A

Figure S10. ESI⁺ QTOF mass spectrum of G₁-6-N

Figure S11. MALDI-TOF mass spectrum (DHB/Na⁺; reflectron mode) of G₁-6-N

Figure S12. MALDI-TOF mass spectrum (DCTB/Na⁺; reflectron mode) of G₂-3-3-A

Figure S13. ESI⁺ QTOF MS spectrum of G₂-3-3-N

Figure S14. MALDI-TOF MS spectrum (DHB/Na⁺; linear mode) of G₂-3-3-N

Figure S15. MALDI-TOF mass spectra (DCTB/Na⁺; reflectron \uparrow /linear \downarrow mode) of G₂-3-6-A

Figure S16. MALDI-TOF mass spectrum (DHB/Na⁺; linear mode) of G₂-3-6-N

Figure S17. MALDI-TOF mass spectrum (DCTB/Na⁺; linear mode) of G₂-6-3-A

Figure S18. MALDI-TOF mass spectrum (DHB/Na⁺; linear mode) of G₂-6-3-N

Figure S19. MALDI-TOF mass spectrum (DCTB/Na⁺; linear mode) of G₂-6-6-A

Figure S20. MALDI-TOF mass spectrum (DHB/Na⁺; linear mode) of G₂-6-6-N

Figure S21. MALDI-TOF mass spectrum (DCTB/Na⁺; linear mode) of G₃-3-3-3-A

Figure S22. MALDI-TOF mass spectrum (DHB/Na⁺; linear mode) of G₃-3-3-3-N

3. Recycling of modules AB₃ and AB₆

Due to the different reactivity of both activated esters, the modules are isolated from the filtrate in different forms, which entails their variant workup. All forms of the smaller AB₃ module present in the filtrates can be easily converted to the free acid, following the procedure used for its preparation from the methyl ester. In contrast, the AB₆ module is recovered as a mixture of free acid, methyl ester, and dimethylamide. Due to the higher hydrolytic stability of amides compared to esters, a longer reaction time and a change in reaction media were necessary for the conversion to AB₆ free acid, and the product was slightly contaminated with residual amide. To simplify the recycling of this module, the dimethylamide formation can presumably be suppressed by using dimethylformamide for peptide synthesis as a solvent for the coupling reaction. Nevertheless, after the aqueous workup, nanofiltration, additional washing and hydrolysis, we were able to recover 91% of the excess AB₆ module employed in the coupling reaction. Comparison of ¹H NMR spectra of both recycled modules with the originally prepared ones are shown below (Figures S23 and S24). Recycled AB₆ module was utilized to prepare G₁-6-A dendrimer; the product was isolated in 89% yield, confirming the applicability of the recycling.

Beneficially, the more stable activated ester BtO-AB₃ can be crystallized from the OSN filtrate and directly used for further synthesis. As proved by the reaction of BtO-AB₃ with the core molecule G₀-N, the coupling proceeds without the addition of TBTU or other activating agents under the common conditions used for amidic coupling. The target G₁-3-A dendrimer was obtained in comparable purity to that prepared from fresh AB₃.

Figure S23: ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) Comparison of proton spectra of recycled and originally prepared (bottom) module AB₃

Figure S24: ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) Comparison of proton spectra of recycled and freshly prepared module AB_6

4. Dynamic light scattering (DLS)

Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS). The size of dendrimers was estimated by multi-angle dynamic light scattering (MADLS)² on Zetasizer Ultra Red (Malvern Panalytical, UK) equipped with a 632.8 nm laser applying detection angles 12.78°, 90.0° and 174.7° in DTS0012 polystyrene cuvettes (Malvern Panalytical, UK). Samples were sonicated for 30 min, filtered through 0.22 µm Nylon syringe filters (Avantor, USA), and measured at a concentration of 5.0 mg/mL in 0.25 % NaCl solution in MeOH. Dendrimers exhibited the lowest tendency to aggregate in this medium compared to pure water, 0.9 % NaCl aqueous solution, and pure MeOH. Each measurement was repeated at least 5 times and the obtained data were analyzed by ZS XPLOER v 3.3.1.5. The presented solvodynamic diameters are mean values from the volume-weighted size distribution.

Optimal concentration determination: 20.0 mg/mL solution of G₂-3-3-N was prepared and diluted 2-fold until 0.31 mg/mL (factor 64×). All prepared solutions were measured and the results compared. From 20.0 to 5.0 mg/mL the observed particle size increased by 16 %, whereas from 5.0 to 0.31 mg/mL the size increased only by less than 5 %. However, from 2.5 to 0.31 mg/mL (from 0.8 to 0.1 nmol/L) the instrument could not reach the standard 300 kcps (kilocounts per second) for side scattering (90.0°) even though setting the highest possible attenuator factor and the quality of correlograms became insufficient. Thus, 5.0 mg/mL was chosen as the optimal concentration for all measurements.

Zeta potential: Zeta potential was measured on the same instrument applying a detection angle 12.78° (forward scattering) in DTS1070 folded capillary Zeta cell (Malvern Panalytical, UK). Samples were sonicated for 30 min, filtered through 0.45 µm Nylon syringe filters (Avantor, USA) and measured at a concentration of 5.0 mg/mL in 0.9 % NaCl aqueous solution (physiological solution). Slow field reversal was avoided (by selecting „monomodal“ analysis model) to prevent electrolysis of the sample. Standard deviation was chosen as a characteristic of variability. Each measurement was repeated 10 times and the obtained data were analyzed by ZS XPLOER v 3.3.1.5.

Table S1. Size differences between dendrimers differing just in the composition of one layer

Generation	Dendrimer 1	Dendrimer 2	ΔR_h (2-1) [nm]	note
1	G ₁ -3-N	G ₁ -6-N	0.8	
2	G ₂ -3-3-N	G ₂ -6-3-N	1.6	<i>inner layer</i>
	G ₂ -3-3-N	G ₂ -3-6-N	1.3	
	G ₂ -3-6-N	G ₂ -6-6-N	1.4	<i>inner layer</i>
	G ₂ -6-3-N	G ₂ -6-6-N	1.1	
3	G ₃ -3-3-3-N	G ₃ -6-3-3-N	2.4	<i>inner layer</i>
	G ₃ -3-3-3-N	G ₃ -3-6-3-N	1.4	
	G ₃ -3-3-3-N	G ₃ -3-3-6-N	2.0	
	G ₃ -3-3-6-N	G ₃ -6-3-6-N	2.1	<i>inner layer</i>
	G ₃ -3-3-6-N	G ₃ -3-6-6-N	1.5	
	G ₃ -3-6-3-N	G ₃ -6-6-3-N	2.9	<i>inner layer</i>
	G ₃ -3-6-3-N	G ₃ -3-6-6-N	2.1	
	G ₃ -6-3-3-N	G ₃ -6-6-3-N	1.9	
	G ₃ -6-3-3-N	G ₃ -6-3-6-N	1.7	
	G ₃ -3-6-6-N	G ₃ -6-6-6-N	2.6	<i>inner layer</i>
	G ₃ -6-3-6-N	G ₃ -6-6-6-N	2.0	
	G ₃ -6-6-3-N	G ₃ -6-6-6-N	1.8	

Figure S25. Volume-weighted size distribution of G₁-3-N.

Figure S26. Volume-weighted size distribution of G₁-6-N.

Figure S27. Volume-weighted size distribution of G₂-3-3-N.

Figure S28. Volume-weighted size distribution of G₂-3-6-N.

Figure S29. Volume-weighted size distribution of G₂-6-3-N.

Figure S30. Volume-weighted size distribution of G₂-6-6-N.

Figure S31. Volume-weighted size distribution of G₃-3-3-3-N.

Figure S32. Volume-weighted size distribution of G₃-3-6-3-N.

Figure S33. Volume-weighted size distribution of G₃-3-3-6-N.

Figure S34. Volume-weighted size distribution of G₃-3-6-6-N.

Figure S35. Volume-weighted size distribution of G₃-6-3-3-N.

Figure S36. Volume-weighted size distribution of G₃-6-6-3-N.

Figure S37. Volume-weighted size distribution of G₃-6-3-6-N.

Figure S38. Volume-weighted size distribution of G₃-6-6-6-N.

5. Diffusion NMR

^1H NMR diffusion data at 25 °C were acquired using Bruker Avance 500 IIIHD NMR spectrometer at magnetic field of 11.75 T with Micro-5 probehead containing ^1H , ^2H radiofrequency (RF) insert and Diff50 z-gradient coil. ^2H field-frequency lock was used. The magnetic field gradient pulses were generated by Bruker GREAT accessory. The samples were prepared by dissolving 10 mg of dendrimer in 0.5 ml of CD_3OD stock solvent, which contained 1.98 mg NaCl per 1 ml of CD_3OD (i.e., NaCl concentration was $33.88 \text{ mmol}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$). If the prepared solution appeared turbid, it was further 1/10 diluted by mixing 20 μl of the solution with 180 μl of CD_3OD stock solvent. The samples were placed into 5 mm outer diameter Shigemi tubes so that the sample lengths did not exceed 1 cm. The stimulated echo pulse sequence with 20 ms diffusion delay and 5 ms longitudinal eddy-current delay was used (these delays contained weak purging 2 ms gradient pulses). The delay between the first two RF pulses in the pulse sequence was 2.7 ms.^{3,4} The gradient pulses framing the diffusion time were of sine bell shape of 1.576 ms duration. The gradient intensity was incremented in 32 steps up to 4.26 T/m at the shape maximum. The delay between subsequent scans including acquisition was 3.6 s (16 scans per measurement).

The data processing was carried out within Bruker Topspin 3.2 software. Integral intensities of separable spectral regions were subject to 1-component and 2-component exponential (Gaussian) decay fittings. The 2-component fits were found justified only for the cases of some solute/solvent peaks overlaps. Thus, only the results of 1-component analyses are presented. The self-diffusion coefficients are obtained as intensity (i.e., the spectral region integral) weighted averages of the coefficients corresponding to 7-10 spectral regions (peaks). There were smaller numbers of useful peaks in cases of the spectra of 1/10 dilute solutions. The presented diffusion coefficients are averages of 3-5 subsequent identical experiments.

6. Asymmetric Flow Field-Flow Fractionation (A4F)

The number-average molar masses (M_n) and dispersities (\mathcal{D}) of the samples were measured by A4F. The solvent and sample delivery part of the system consisted of an Agilent G1310A pump, a G1322A degasser, and a G1329A autosampler. The field-flow fractionation long channel was assembled with a 350 μm spacer and a regenerated cellulose membrane with a cutoff of 10 000 g/mol. Three detectors were used in series: a Spectromonitor 3200 UV/VIS unit (Thermo Separation Products, Fremont, USA), a Wyatt Optilab-rEX RI detector, and a Wyatt Dawn 8+ multiangle light-scattering unit. Wyatt software Astra V (version 5.3.4.15) controlled all system components through a Wyatt ECLIPSE 3+ unit.

Water with azide was used as a solvent. The samples were filtered through a 0.45 μm PVDF filter before injection. Molar mass measurements were conducted with a constant detector flow rate of 1.0 mL/min. The focusing time was 5 min at a cross-flow of 3.5 mL/min. The injection flow was 0.2 mL/min, and 100 μL of the sample was injected in all cases. After the focusing step, the cross-flow was linearly decreased from 2.5 mL/min to 0.1 mL/min in 35 min and was then kept constant at 0.1 mL/min for the next 15 min, followed by 15 min without cross-flow.

The water of MilliQ purity was prepared by a laboratory water purification system, Milli-Q® IQ 7000 (Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany), and sodium azide (NaN_3 ; $\geq 99\%$, Lach-Ner, 0.2 g/L) as an antibacterial agent was used.

Concentration: 3.152 mg/mL

Results

Peak Results

	Peak 1
Masses	
Calculated Mass (μg)	315.18
Mass Recovery (%)	100.0
Mass Fraction (%)	100.0
Molar mass moments (g/mol)	
Mn	3.156×10^4 ($\pm 2.328\%$)
Mp	2.732×10^4 ($\pm 1.952\%$)
Mv	n/a
Mw	3.512×10^4 ($\pm 2.443\%$)
Mz	4.614×10^4 ($\pm 5.971\%$)
Mz+1	8.089×10^4 ($\pm 6.447\%$)
M(avg)	3.919×10^4 ($\pm 0.182\%$)
Polydispersity	
Mw/Mn	1.113 ($\pm 3.375\%$)
Mz/Mn	1.462 ($\pm 6.409\%$)
rms radius moments (nm)	
rn	n/a
rw	n/a
rz	5.0 ($\pm 358.0\%$)
r(avg)	12.4 ($\pm 3.9\%$)

Figure S39. A4F report of G₂-6-6-N

Concentration: 3.057 mg/mL

Results

Peak Results

	Peak 1
Masses	
Calculated Mass (μg)	305.65
Mass Recovery (%)	100.0
Mass Fraction (%)	100.0
Molar mass moments (g/mol)	
Mn	3.216×10^4 ($\pm 2.021\%$)
Mp	2.915×10^4 ($\pm 1.950\%$)
Mv	n/a
Mw	3.314×10^4 ($\pm 2.024\%$)
Mz	3.414×10^4 ($\pm 4.543\%$)
Mz+1	3.545×10^4 ($\pm 7.088\%$)
M(avg)	3.019×10^4 ($\pm 0.147\%$)
Polydispersity	
Mw/Mn	1.030 ($\pm 2.860\%$)
Mz/Mn	1.062 ($\pm 4.973\%$)
rms radius moments (nm)	
rn	11.6 ($\pm 59.0\%$)
rw	12.2 ($\pm 52.7\%$)
rz	12.8 ($\pm 48.4\%$)
r(avg)	9.5 ($\pm 7.2\%$)

Figure S40. A4F report of G₃-3-3-3-N

Concentration: 2.632 mg/mL

Results

Peak Results

	Peak 1
Masses	
Calculated Mass (μg)	263.20
Mass Recovery (%)	100.0
Mass Fraction (%)	100.0
Molar mass moments (g/mol)	
Mn	6.197×10^4 ($\pm 2.743\%$)
Mp	5.748×10^4 ($\pm 2.589\%$)
Mv	n/a
Mw	7.237×10^4 ($\pm 2.163\%$)
Mz	1.153×10^5 ($\pm 4.264\%$)
Mz+1	3.329×10^5 ($\pm 1.991\%$)
M(avg)	8.253×10^4 ($\pm 0.097\%$)
Polydispersity	
Mw/Mn	1.168 ($\pm 3.493\%$)
Mz/Mn	1.860 ($\pm 5.070\%$)
rms radius moments (nm)	
rn	28.7 ($\pm 18.6\%$)
rw	27.6 ($\pm 16.1\%$)
rz	27.5 ($\pm 15.4\%$)
r(avg)	23.7 ($\pm 0.6\%$)

Figure S41. A4F report of G₃-3-3-6-N

Concentration: 3.384 mg/mL

Results

Peak Results

	Peak 1
Masses	
Calculated Mass (μg)	338.41
Mass Recovery (%)	100.0
Mass Fraction (%)	100.0
Molar mass moments (g/mol)	
Mn	6.365×10^4 ($\pm 2.875\%$)
Mp	5.466×10^4 ($\pm 2.565\%$)
Mv	n/a
Mw	7.047×10^4 ($\pm 3.098\%$)
Mz	8.157×10^4 ($\pm 7.173\%$)
Mz+1	9.849×10^4 ($\pm 9.737\%$)
M(avg)	7.657×10^4 ($\pm 0.166\%$)
Polydispersity	
Mw/Mn	1.107 ($\pm 4.227\%$)
Mz/Mn	1.282 ($\pm 7.727\%$)
rms radius moments (nm)	
rn	21.9 ($\pm 21.0\%$)
rw	24.0 ($\pm 18.0\%$)
rz	26.4 ($\pm 15.8\%$)
r(avg)	14.0 ($\pm 2.5\%$)

Figure S42. A4F report of G₃-3-6-3-N

Concentration: 3.049 mg/mL

Results

Peak Results

	Peak 1
Masses	
Calculated Mass (μg)	304.92
Mass Recovery (%)	100.0
Mass Fraction (%)	100.0
Molar mass moments (g/mol)	
Mn	5.368×10^4 ($\pm 2.832\%$)
Mp	4.762×10^4 ($\pm 2.644\%$)
Mv	n/a
Mw	5.925×10^4 ($\pm 3.202\%$)
Mz	6.893×10^4 ($\pm 7.739\%$)
Mz+1	8.399×10^4 ($\pm 11.101\%$)
M(avg)	6.207×10^4 ($\pm 0.182\%$)
Polydispersity	
Mw/Mn	1.104 ($\pm 4.275\%$)
Mz/Mn	1.284 ($\pm 8.241\%$)
rms radius moments (nm)	
rn	9.2 ($\pm 114.9\%$)
rw	12.9 ($\pm 61.7\%$)
rz	15.8 ($\pm 44.6\%$)
r(avg)	24.2 ($\pm 4.0\%$)

Figure S43. A4F report of G₃-6-3-3-N

Concentration: 2.836 mg/mL

Results

Peak Results

Peak 1	
Masses	
Calculated Mass (μg)	283.63
Mass Recovery (%)	100.0
Mass Fraction (%)	100.0
Molar mass moments (g/mol)	
Mn	1.079×10^5 ($\pm 1.980\%$)
Mp	8.815×10^4 ($\pm 1.791\%$)
Mv	n/a
Mw	1.312×10^5 ($\pm 2.105\%$)
Mz	1.859×10^5 ($\pm 4.668\%$)
Mz+1	2.855×10^5 ($\pm 4.744\%$)
M(avg)	1.350×10^5 ($\pm 0.106\%$)
Polydispersity	
Mw/Mn	1.215 ($\pm 2.890\%$)
Mz/Mn	1.722 ($\pm 5.071\%$)
rms radius moments (nm)	
rn	4.9 ($\pm 291.1\%$)
rw	8.1 ($\pm 111.4\%$)
rz	10.2 ($\pm 71.9\%$)
r(avg)	8.8 ($\pm 7.0\%$)

Figure S44. A4F report of G₃-3-6-6-N

Concentration: 3.229 mg/mL

Results

Peak Results

Peak 1	
Masses	
Calculated Mass (μg)	322.90
Mass Recovery (%)	100.0
Mass Fraction (%)	100.0
Molar mass moments (g/mol)	
Mn	1.675×10^5 ($\pm 3.350\%$)
Mp	1.372×10^5 ($\pm 3.597\%$)
Mv	n/a
Mw	2.426×10^5 ($\pm 4.041\%$)
Mz	4.202×10^5 ($\pm 9.184\%$)
Mz+1	6.880×10^5 ($\pm 8.657\%$)
M(avg)	1.900×10^5 ($\pm 0.180\%$)
Polydispersity	
Mw/Mn	1.448 ($\pm 5.250\%$)
Mz/Mn	2.509 ($\pm 9.776\%$)
rms radius moments (nm)	
rn	22.5 ($\pm 21.2\%$)
rw	28.2 ($\pm 15.0\%$)
rz	34.5 ($\pm 11.2\%$)
r(avg)	13.5 ($\pm 2.4\%$)

Figure S45. A4F report of G₃-6-3-6-N

Concentration: 3.311 mg/mL

Results

Peak Results

	Peak 1
Masses	
Calculated Mass (μg)	331.06
Mass Recovery (%)	100.0
Mass Fraction (%)	100.0
Molar mass moments (g/mol)	
Mn	4.165×10^5 ($\pm 1.713\%$)
Mp	3.288×10^5 ($\pm 1.670\%$)
Mv	n/a
Mw	5.678×10^5 ($\pm 1.778\%$)
Mz	1.034×10^6 ($\pm 4.078\%$)
Mz+1	1.820×10^6 ($\pm 3.804\%$)
M(avg)	4.732×10^5 ($\pm 0.109\%$)
Polydispersity	
Mw/Mn	1.363 ($\pm 2.469\%$)
Mz/Mn	2.482 ($\pm 4.424\%$)
rms radius moments (nm)	
rn	7.7 ($\pm 120.3\%$)
rw	8.2 ($\pm 105.9\%$)
rz	9.6 ($\pm 80.4\%$)
r(avg)	10.3 ($\pm 3.4\%$)

Figure S46. A4F report of G₃-6-6-3-N

Concentration: 2.877 mg/mL

Results

Peak Results

Peak 1

Masses

Calculated Mass (μg)	287.67
Mass Recovery (%)	100.0
Mass Fraction (%)	100.0

Molar mass moments (g/mol)

Mn	2.321×10^5 ($\pm 2.413\%$)
Mp	1.928×10^5 ($\pm 2.384\%$)
Mv	n/a
Mw	2.930×10^5 ($\pm 2.435\%$)
Mz	4.695×10^5 ($\pm 5.476\%$)
Mz+1	8.062×10^5 ($\pm 5.173\%$)
M(avg)	2.904×10^5 ($\pm 0.145\%$)

Polydispersity

Mw/Mn	1.263 ($\pm 3.428\%$)
Mz/Mn	2.023 ($\pm 5.984\%$)

rms radius moments (nm)

rn	6.2 ($\pm 236.5\%$)
rw	6.8 ($\pm 196.5\%$)
rz	7.8 ($\pm 150.3\%$)
r(avg)	10.2 ($\pm 4.8\%$)

Figure S47. A4F report of G₃-6-6-N

7. Molecular modelling

3D computer models of dendrimers were created using dendrimer builder, as implemented in the Materials Studio software package from BIOVIA (formerly Accelrys). The AM1-BCC technique⁵ was used to calculate the partial charges of dendrimer atoms. For this charge parametrization, the Amber program Antechamber was used. The GAFF force field (General Amber Force Field)⁶ was used for parameterization of all dendrimer structures. Missing force constants and energy barriers for “Si containing” force field terms were fitted by minimizing the differences between QM and force field based relative energies of 100 configurations of properly chosen molecular fragment (i.e. ff parameters that most accurately ensures the following requirement were used: $E_{i_force-field} = E_{i_quantum} + K$ for all configurations i - where $E_{i_force-field}$ and $E_{i_quantum}$ are force field and QM based energy of molecular configuration i and K is constant). Equilibrium values of “Si-containing” bonds and angles were obtained using QM optimization of the given molecular fragment. QM energies were calculated at MP2/HF/6-31G** level of theory using GAMESS⁷, and fitting was accomplished using the paramfit routine from AMBER software.⁸ Slightly adjusted van der Waals parameters for Si atoms from MM3 force field⁹ were used in this study. All the calculated and used values of the-Si-containing force field parameters are available in the supporting information of our previous work.¹⁰ Dendrimers were solvated in methanol in a cube simulation box – see Fig. S48. The minimal distance from dendrimer atoms to the wall of the simulation box was set to 20 Å. A proper number of Cl⁻ and Na⁺ ions was added to preserve the neutrality of the system and to ensure the bulk concentration used in the DLS experiment (0.25 % NaCl solution in MeOH). First, the systems were minimized (5000 steps with 2 kcal/(mol Å²) restraint + 50000 without restraint), heated (200 ps NVT) to 298 K and equilibrated using 20 ns (for G₁,G₂) and 30 ns (for G₃) long molecular dynamics simulations (NPT, T = 298 K, P = 0.1 MPa). The first 0.5 ns with restrained solute. Hydrogens were constrained with the SHAKE algorithm to allow 2 fs time step¹¹ and a Langevin thermostat with collision frequency 2 ps⁻¹ was used for all MD runs.¹² The pressure relaxation time for weak-coupling barostat was 2 ps. Particle mesh Ewald method (PME) was used to treat long range electrostatic interactions under periodic conditions with a direct space cutoff of 10 Å. The same cutoff was used for van der Waals interactions. The pmemd.cuda module¹³ from Amber20 package was used for all simulation steps. All, third generation dendrimers and some of the second generation dendrimers (G₂-6-3-N, G₂-6-6-N) were before simulation in MeOH first shortly simulated in vacuum, to obtain more extended structures (thanks to the positive net charge), which almost eliminated eventual partly intertwined branches problem of the initial structures. The eventual remaining problems were solved manually on these extended structures by proper changes of relevant bond angles or torsional angles. Structural analyses (RDF, Rg, Rmax) were performed using the CPPTRAJ routine from Amber. The last 5 ns of the MD trajectories were used for these analyses. UCSF Chimera software was used for all visualizations as well as for the manual corrections of the dendrimer structures.¹⁴

Figure S48. Example of the initial simulation box with dendrimer (G_3 -6-6-6-N) solvated in MeOH with Na^+ , Cl^- ions. Colors: C – grey/black; O – red; H – white; Si – beige; N – blue; S – yellow, Cl^- anions – green, Na^+ cations - purple.

Figure S49. Radial distribution functions (relative density profiles (RDF)) of selected atoms, with respect to central Si atom, or just RDF of the given homogenous set of atoms, in case of simulated dendrimer G_1-3-N .

Figure S50. Radial distribution functions (relative density profiles (RDF)) of selected atoms, with respect to central Si atom, or just RDF of the given homogenous set of atoms, in case of simulated dendrimer G_1-6-N .

Figure S51. Radial distribution functions (relative density profiles (RDF)) of selected atoms, with respect to central Si atom, or just RDF of the given homogenous set of atoms, in case of simulated dendrimer $G_2-3-3-N$.

Figure S52.: Radial distribution functions (relative density profiles (RDF)) of selected atoms, with respect to central Si atom, or just RDF of the given homogenous set of atoms, in case of simulated dendrimer $G_2-3-6-N$.

Figure S53. Radial distribution functions (relative density profiles (RDF)) of selected atoms, with respect to central Si atom, or just RDF of the given homogenous set of atoms, in case of simulated dendrimer G₂-6-3-N.

Figure S54. Radial distribution functions (relative density profiles (RDF)) of selected atoms, with respect to central Si atom, or just RDF of the given homogenous set of atoms, in case of simulated dendrimer G₂-6-6-N.

Figure S55. Radial distribution functions (relative density profiles (RDF)) of selected atoms, with respect to central Si atom, or just RDF of the given homogenous set of atoms, in case of simulated dendrimer G₃-3-3-3-N.

Figure S56. Radial distribution functions (relative density profiles (RDF)) of selected atoms, with respect to central Si atom, or just RDF of the given homogenous set of atoms, in case of simulated dendrimer G₃-3-3-6-N.

Figure S57. Radial distribution functions (relative density profiles (RDF)) of selected atoms, with respect to central Si atom, or just RDF of the given homogenous set of atoms, in case of simulated dendrimer $G_3-3-6-3-N$.

Figure S58. Radial distribution functions (relative density profiles (RDF)) of selected atoms, with respect to central Si atom, or just RDF of the given homogenous set of atoms, in case of simulated dendrimer $G_3-3-6-6-N$.

Figure S59. Radial distribution functions (relative density profiles (RDF)) of selected atoms, with respect to central Si atom, or just RDF of the given homogenous set of atoms, in case of simulated dendrimer $G_3-6-3-N$.

Figure S60. Radial distribution functions (relative density profiles (RDF)) of selected atoms, with respect to central Si atom, or just RDF of the given homogenous set of atoms, in case of simulated dendrimer $G_3-6-3-6-N$.

Figure S61. Radial distribution functions (relative density profiles (RDF)) of selected atoms, with respect to central Si atom, or just RDF of the given homogenous set of atoms, in case of simulated dendrimer $G_3-6-6-3-N$.

Figure S62. Radial distribution functions (relative density profiles (RDF)) of selected atoms, with respect to central Si atom, or just RDF of the given homogenous set of atoms, in case of simulated dendrimer $G_3-6-6-6-N$.

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9. NMR spektra

Figure S63: ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) $\text{G}_0\text{-N}$

Figure S66: 1H - 1H COSY NMR (DMSO- d_6) G_0-N

Figure S67: 1H - ^{13}C HSQC NMR (DMSO- d_6) G_0-N

Figure S68: ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) MeO-AB₃

Figure S69: ¹³C {¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) MeO-AB₃

Figure S76: ^{29}Si $\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (79 MHz, CDCl_3) **AB₃**

Figure S77: ^1H - ^1H COSY NMR (CDCl_3) **AB₃**

Figure S80: ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) BtO-AB₃

Figure S81: ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) BtO-AB₃

Figure S82: ^1H - ^1H COSY NMR (CDCl_3) BtO-AB₃

Figure S83: ^1H - ^{13}C HSQC NMR (CDCl_3) BtO-AB₃

Figure S88: ^1H - ^1H COSY NMR (CDCl_3) **G₁-3-A**

Figure S89: ^1H - ^{13}C HSQC NMR (CDCl_3) **G₁-3-A**

Figure S90: ^1H - ^{13}C HMBC NMR (CDCl_3) **G₁-3-A**

Figure S94: ^1H - ^1H COSY NMR (DMSO- d_6) $\text{G}_1\text{-3-N}$

Figure S95: ^1H - ^{13}C HSQC NMR (DMSO- d_6) $\text{G}_1\text{-3-N}$

Figure S98: ¹³C {¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) **G₁-6-A**

Figure S99: ²⁹Si {¹H} NMR (79 MHz, CDCl₃) **G₁-6-A**

Figure S100: ^1H - ^1H COSY NMR (CDCl_3) **G₁-6-A**

Figure S101: ^1H - ^{13}C HSQC NMR (CDCl_3) **G₁-6-A**

Figure S102: ^1H - ^{13}C HMBC NMR (CDCl_3) **G₁-6-A**

Figure S103: ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) **G₁-6-N**

Figure S104: ¹³C {¹H} NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) **G₁-6-N**

Figure S105: ²⁹Si {¹H} NMR (79 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) **G₁-6-N**

Figure S106: ^1H - ^1H COSY NMR (DMSO- d_6) G₁-6-N

Figure S107: ^1H - ^{13}C HSQC NMR (DMSO- d_6) G₁-6-N

Figure S108: ^1H - ^{13}C HMBC NMR (DMSO- d_6) $\text{G}_1\text{-6-N}$

Figure S109: ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) $\text{G}_2\text{-3-3-A}$

Figure S110: ¹³C {¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) **G₂-3-3-A**

Figure S111: ²⁹Si {¹H} NMR (79 MHz, CDCl₃) **G₂-3-3-A**

Figure S114: ^1H - ^{13}C HMBC NMR (CDCl_3) $\text{G}_2\text{-3-3-A}$

Figure S115: ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) $\text{G}_2\text{-3-3-N}$

Figure S116: ¹³C {¹H} NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) G₂-3-3-N

Figure S117: ²⁹Si {¹H} NMR (79 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) G₂-3-3-N

Figure S118: ^1H - ^1H COSY NMR (DMSO- d_6) G₂-3-3-N

Figure S119: ^1H - ^{13}C HSQC NMR (DMSO- d_6) G₂-3-3-N

Figure S120: ^1H - ^{13}C HMBC NMR ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) $\text{G}_2\text{-3-3-N}$

Figure S121: ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) $\text{G}_2\text{-3-6-A}$

Figure S122: ^{13}C $\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) G₂-3-6-A

Figure S123: ^{29}Si $\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (79 MHz, CDCl_3) G₂-3-6-A

Figure S124: ^1H - ^1H COSY NMR (CDCl_3) **G₂-3-6-A**

Figure S125: ^1H - ^{13}C HSQC NMR (CDCl_3) **G₂-3-6-A**

Figure S126: ^1H - ^{13}C HMBC NMR (CDCl_3) **G₂-3-6-A**

Figure S127: ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) **G₂-3-6-N**

Figure S128: ^{13}C $\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) G₂-3-6-N

Figure S129: ^{29}Si $\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (79 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) G₂-3-6-N

Figure S132: ^1H - ^{13}C HMBC NMR (DMSO- d_6) G₂-3-6-N

Figure S134: ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) G₂-6-3-A

Figure S137: ^1H - ^1H COSY NMR (CDCl_3) **G₂-6-3-A**

Figure S138: ^1H - ^{13}C HSQC NMR (CDCl_3) **G₂-6-3-A**

Figure S139: ^1H - ^{13}C HMBC NMR (CDCl_3) **G₂-6-3-A**

Figure S140: ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) **G₂-6-3-N**

Figure S141: ¹³C {¹H} NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) G₂-6-3-N

Figure S142: ²⁹Si {¹H} NMR (79 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) G₂-6-3-N

Figure S143: ^1H - ^1H COSY NMR (DMSO- d_6) G₂-6-3-N

Figure S144: ^1H - ^{13}C HSQC NMR (DMSO- d_6) G₂-6-3-N

Figure S145: ^1H - ^{13}C HMBC NMR (DMSO- d_6) G₂-6-3-N

Figure S146: ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) G₂-6-6-A

Figure S147: ^{13}C $\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) G₂-6-6-A

Figure S148: ^{29}Si $\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (79 MHz, CDCl_3) G₂-6-6-A

Figure S149: ^1H - ^1H COSY NMR (CDCl_3) **G₂-6-6-A**

Figure S150: ^1H - ^{13}C HSQC NMR (CDCl_3) **G₂-6-6-A**

Figure S151: ^1H - ^{13}C HMBC NMR (CDCl_3) **G₂-6-6-A**

Figure S152: ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) **G₂-6-6-N**

Figure S153 ¹³C {¹H} NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) G₂-6-6-N

Figure S154: ²⁹Si {¹H} NMR (79 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) G₂-6-6-N

Figure S155: ^1H - ^1H COSY NMR (DMSO- d_6) **G₂-6-6-N**

Figure S156: ^1H - ^{13}C HSQC NMR (DMSO- d_6) **G₂-6-6-N**

Figure S161: ^1H - ^1H COSY NMR (CDCl_3) **G₃-3-3-3-A**

Figure S162: ^1H - ^{13}C HSQC NMR (CDCl_3) **G₃-3-3-3-A**

Figure S163: ^1H - ^{13}C HMBC NMR (CDCl_3) $\text{G}_3\text{-3-3-3-A}$

Figure S164: ^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d_6) $\text{G}_3\text{-3-3-3-N}$

Figure S165: ¹H NMR (400 MHz, 100°C, DMSO-*d*₆) **G₃-3-3-3-N**

Figure S166: ¹³C {¹H} NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) **G₃-3-3-3-N**

Figure S169: ^1H - ^{13}C HSQC NMR (DMSO- d_6) $\text{G}_3\text{-3-3-3-N}$

Figure S170: ^1H - ^{13}C HMBC NMR (DMSO- d_6) $\text{G}_3\text{-3-3-3-N}$

Figure S175: ^1H - ^{13}C HSQC NMR (CDCl_3) **G₃-3-3-6-A**

Figure S176: ^1H - ^{13}C HMBC NMR (CDCl_3) **G₃-3-3-6-A**

Figure S177: ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) G₃-3-3-6-N

Figure S178: ¹H NMR (400 MHz, 100°C, DMSO-*d*₆) G₃-3-3-6-N

Figure S181: ^1H - ^1H COSY NMR (DMSO- d_6) **G₃-3-3-6-N**

Figure S182: ^1H - ^{13}C HSQC NMR (DMSO- d_6) **G₃-3-3-6-N**

Figure S183: ^1H - ^{13}C HMBC NMR (DMSO- d_6) $\text{G}_3\text{-3-3-6-N}$

Figure S184: ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) $\text{G}_3\text{-3-6-3-A}$

Figure S189: ^1H - ^{13}C HMBC NMR (CDCl_3) $\text{G}_3\text{-3-6-3-A}$

Figure S190: ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) $\text{G}_3\text{-3-6-3-N}$

Figure S191: ^1H NMR (400 MHz, 100°C, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) $\text{G}_3\text{-3-6-3-N}$

Figure S192: ^{13}C $\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) $\text{G}_3\text{-3-6-3-N}$

Figure S193: ²⁹Si {¹H} NMR (79 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) G₃-3-6-3-N

Figure S194: ¹H-¹H COSY NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) G₃-3-6-3-N

Figure S195: ^1H - ^{13}C HSQC NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) **G₃-3-6-3-N**

Figure S196: ^1H - ^{13}C HSQC NMR (100°C , $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) **G₃-3-6-3-N**

Figure S197: ^1H - ^{13}C HMBC NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) $\text{G}_3\text{-3-6-3-N}$

Figure S198: ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) $\text{G}_3\text{-3-6-6-A}$

Figure S199: ¹³C {¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) G₃-3-6-6-A

Figure S200: ²⁹Si {¹H} NMR (79 MHz, CDCl₃) G₃-3-6-6-A

Figure S201: ^1H - ^1H COSY NMR (CDCl_3) **G₃-3-6-6-A**

Figure S202: ^1H - ^{13}C HSQC NMR (CDCl_3) **G₃-3-6-6-A**

Figure S205: ¹H NMR (400 MHz, 100°C, DMSO-*d*₆) G₃-3-6-6-N

Figure S206: ¹³C {¹H} NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) G₃-3-6-6-N

Figure S209: ^1H - ^{13}C HSQC NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) $\text{G}_3\text{-3-6-6-N}$

Figure S210: ^1H - ^{13}C HMBC NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) $\text{G}_3\text{-3-6-6-N}$

Figure S219: ^{13}C $\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, DMSO- d_6) G₃-6-3-3-N

Figure S220: ^{29}Si $\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (79 MHz, DMSO- d_6) G₃-6-3-3-N

Figure S221: ^1H - ^1H COSY NMR (DMSO- d_6) G₃-6-3-3-N

Figure S222: ^1H - ^{13}C HSQC NMR (DMSO- d_6) G₃-6-3-3-N

Figure S225: ¹³C {¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) G₃-6-3-6-A

Figure S226: ²⁹Si {¹H} NMR (79 MHz, CDCl₃) G₃-6-3-6-A

Figure S229: ^1H - ^{13}C HMBC NMR (CDCl_3) $\text{G}_3\text{-6-3-6-A}$

Figure S230: ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) $\text{G}_3\text{-6-3-6-N}$

Figure S231: ¹H NMR (400 MHz, 100°C, DMSO-*d*₆) G₃-6-3-6-N

Figure S232: ¹³C {¹H} NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) G₃-6-3-6-N

Figure S233: ²⁹Si {¹H} NMR (79 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) G₃-6-3-6-N

Figure S234: ¹H-¹H COSY NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) G₃-6-3-6-N

Figure S239: ²⁹Si {¹H} NMR (79 MHz, CDCl₃) G₃-6-6-3-A

Figure S240: ¹H-¹H COSY NMR (CDCl₃) G₃-6-6-3-A

Figure S243: ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) G₃-6-6-3-N

Figure S244: ¹H NMR (400 MHz, 100°C, DMSO-*d*₆) G₃-6-6-3-N

Figure S245: ^{13}C $\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) **G₃-6-6-3-N**

Figure S246: ^{29}Si $\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (79 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) **G₃-6-6-3-N**

Figure S247: ^1H - ^1H COSY NMR (DMSO- d_6) G₃-6-6-3-N

Figure S248: ^1H - ^{13}C HSQC NMR (DMSO- d_6) G₃-6-6-3-N

Figure S249: ^1H - ^{13}C HMBC NMR ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) $\text{G}_3\text{-6-6-3-N}$

Figure S250: ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) $\text{G}_3\text{-6-6-6-A}$

Figure S251: ¹³C {¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) G₃-6-6-6-A

Figure S252: ²⁹Si {¹H} NMR (79 MHz, CDCl₃) G₃-6-6-6-A

Figure S255 ^1H - ^{13}C HMBC NMR (CDCl_3) **G₃-6-6-6-A**

Figure S256: ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) **G₃-6-6-6-N**

Figure S257: ¹H NMR (400 MHz, 100°C, DMSO-*d*₆) **G₃-6-6-6-N**

Figure S258: ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CD₃OD) **G₃-6-6-6-N**

Figure S259: ¹³C {¹H} NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) G₃-6-6-6-N

Figure S260: ²⁹Si {¹H} NMR (79 MHz, CD₃OD) G₃-6-6-6-N

Figure S263: ^1H - ^{13}C HMBC NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) **G₃-6-6-6-N**